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Elemental composition and mineralogy of NW Venezuelan Guasare coals: Provenance study and role of illite in methane sorption capacity --Manuscript Draft--

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Corresponding Author:	Gonzalo Marquez, PhD University of Huelva: Universidad de Huelva Huelva, Huelva SPAIN
First Author:	Gonzalo Marquez, PhD
Order of Authors:	Gonzalo Marquez, PhD M. MARTÍNEZ, PhD G. CARRUYO, Dra C. BOENTE, PhD E. LORENZO, Dra R. TOCCO, MSc
Abstract:	<p>A series of coal seams (groups 4 to 11) of Paleocene age in the Marcelina Formation have been open pit exploited in two mines (Paso Diablo and Mina Norte) in the Guasare Coalfield (NW Venezuela). An investigation has been conducted on the elemental composition, mineralogy, and coalbed methane (CBM) in Guasare coals. For this study, 46 core coal samples of 16 seams (groups 2 to 7) were collected from 16 exploratory boreholes that were drilled in both mines. It was also considered unpublished proximate-ultimate and gross calorific data of other 66 coals of 31 seams intersected in most of these wells. The coals under study showed low ash yields (3.4 wt. % on average) and were classified as high volatile bituminous A. Mean values of trace element and lanthanide (REE) contents in Marcelina coals generally indicate depletion compared to average values for world hard coals. The statistical evaluations indicate that elements (except Se) show inorganic affinity or intermediate association and mixed mode of occurrence. La/Sc, Th/Sc, La/Co, and Th/Cr ratios support a felsic or metamorphic felsic source for the mineral matter present in Marcelina coals. Most coal samples exhibited similar normalized REE patterns, showing light REE enriched, as well as negative Ce and Eu anomalies. The comparison of REE patterns to those of some nearby granitoids suggests that Marcelina coals received a supply of sediments from these granitic source rocks. The mineralogical compositions of representative coal samples are notably similar, kaolinite and quartz were noted as the major mineral species in all coal seams. The measured gas volumes available for CBM production from Marcelina seams vary approximately between 5 and 11 cm³/g. Variation in the illite content has an appreciable positive effect on gas adsorption capacity of Guasare coals. Lastly, a numerical model of the gas generative potential of the coals in the Marcelina Formation was also developed.</p>
Suggested Reviewers:	<p>Katya Reategui, Dra. Associate Professor, Central University of Venezuela katya.reategui@ciens.ucv.ve Expertise in gas and petroleum geochemistry from the region of the study area.</p> <p>Javier Alejandro, Dr Full Professor, University of Seville falejan@us.es He is a very good specialist in mineralogy, particularly clays, in coals and other rocks</p> <p>Tatiana M. Juliao, Dra.</p>

	<p>Senior Researcher, Ecopetrol tatianajuliao@ecopetrol.com.co She is an expert in coal geology and her Master's thesis was about Guasare coals and their CBM resources</p>
	<p>Cristina Rodrigues, Dra. Associate Professor, Fernando Pessoa University cfrodrig@gmail.com Expertise in coals and CBM</p>
<p>Opposed Reviewers:</p>	
<p>Response to Reviewers:</p>	

Dear Dr. Frank Audemard:

I am submitting the last modified version of the manuscript entitled “**Elemental composition and mineralogy of NW Venezuelan Guasare coals: Provenance study and role of illite in methane sorption capacity**” for your considerations in order to be published in International Journal of South American Earth Sciences.

Attached you can find highlights, manuscript, figures, tables and appendices.

Yours sincerely,

Dr. Gonzalo Márquez

Dear Dr. F. Audemard:

All minor changes have been carried out in the last revised manuscript. Harvard (name-date) reference style was adequately followed.

Please, be aware of changes (**greenish colour**) in the text.

Enclosed you will find the text, figures and tables.

Yours sincerely, Dr. G. Marquez

Element contents in Marcelina coals suggest depletion in relation to world hard coals

Guasare coals received a supply of sediments from nearby granitoids based on REE data

A numerical modeling of the gas generative potential of Guasare coals was developed

Measured methane sorption capacity of raw coal samples range between 5 and 12 cm³/g

Variation in the illite content impacts on gas adsorption capacity of Guasare coals

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Elemental composition and mineralogy of NW Venezuelan Guasare coals: Provenance study and role of illite in methane sorption capacity

G. MÁRQUEZ^{a,*}, M. MARTÍNEZ^b, G. CARRUYO^c, C. BOENTE^a, E. LORENZO^d and R. TOCCO^e

^a Center for Research in Sustainable Chemistry (CIQSO), University of Huelva, 21006 Huelva, Spain

^b Institute of Earth Sciences, Faculty of Sciences, Central University of Venezuela, Caracas 3895-1010A, Venezuela

^c School of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, University of Zulia, Maracaibo 4002-A, Venezuela

^d School of Engineering Sciences, State University Santa Elena Peninsula, 240204 La Libertad, Ecuador

^e Independent Petroleum Geochemistry Consultant, Madrid, 28410, Spain

Abstract: A series of coal seams (groups 4 to 11) of Paleocene age in the Marcelina Formation have been open pit exploited in two mines (Paso Diablo and Mina Norte) in the Guasare Coalfield (NW Venezuela). An investigation has been conducted on the elemental composition, mineralogy, and coalbed methane (CBM) in Guasare coals. For this study, 46 core coal samples of 16 seams (groups 2 to 7) were collected from 16 exploratory boreholes that were drilled in both mines. It was also considered unpublished proximate-ultimate and gross calorific data of other 66 coals of 31 seams intersected in most of these wells. The coals under study showed low ash yields (3.4 wt. % on average) and were classified as high volatile bituminous A. Mean values of trace element and lanthanide (REE) contents in Marcelina coals generally indicate depletion compared to average values for world hard coals. The statistical evaluations indicate that elements (except Se) show inorganic affinity or intermediate association and mixed mode of occurrence. La/Sc, Th/Sc, La/Co, and Th/Cr ratios support a felsic or metamorphic felsic source for the mineral matter present in Marcelina coals. Most coal samples exhibited similar normalized REE patterns, showing light REE enriched, as well as negative Ce and Eu anomalies. The comparison of REE patterns to those of some nearby granitoids suggests that Marcelina coals received a supply of sediments from these granitic source rocks. The mineralogical compositions of representative coal samples are notably similar, kaolinite and quartz were noted as the major mineral species in all coal seams. The measured gas volumes available for CBM production from Marcelina seams vary approximately between 5 and 11 cm³/g. Variation in the illite content has an appreciable positive effect on gas adsorption capacity of Guasare coals. Lastly, a numerical model of the gas generative potential of the coals in the Marcelina Formation was also developed.

Key-words: bituminous coal, Guasare Coalfield, elemental composition, mineralogy, CBM, illite content.

1. Introduction

Venezuela hosts potential resources of approximately ten billion metric tons of coal, 80 percent of them located in the Paleocene aged Guasare Coalfield (e.g., Carruyo, 2017). This basin stretches over a relatively small (55×5 km) geographical zone in the NW sector of Zulia State (Fig. 1a), 85 km northwest of the city of Maracaibo (Escobar et al., 1997). The Guasare Coalfield contains the majority (~1.6 billion tons) of the Venezuelan bituminous coal reserves and holds about 30 coal

seams in the Paleocene Marcelina Formation, with good lateral continuity and thicknesses ranging from 2 to 13 m (Quintero et al., 2011; Escobar et al., 2016). The Marcelina coal seams have been exploited in two mines (Paso Diablo and Mina Norte), operated by open-cast methods, since 1987 (Carruyo, 2017). The Paso Diablo mine and the nearby Mina Norte open-pit are located in the eastern flank of the Sierra de Perijá, between the Oca Fault northwards and the Totumo-Inciarte uplift southwards (Fig. 1b). According to Hackley and Martínez (2007), coal seams in both mines are classified into 11 groups (numbered from bottom to top; see Fig. 2) which, in turn, have been divided into seams so that the stratigraphically highest bed is assigned a Latin capital letter and each of the next lower seams are given letters farther down along the alphabet.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Previous geological studies have been conducted on the mineable and unmined Marcelina coal seams (e.g., Martínez et al., 1989; Juliao, 2010). The Guasare Coalfield has been studied in terms of coal-bed methane potential (Canónico, 2002; Tyler et al., 2006), petrography (Hackley and Martínez, 2007; Escobar et al., 2016), palynology (Pardo, 2004; Petersen et al., 2009), and organic geochemistry (Canónico et al., 2004; Quintero et al., 2011; Escobar et al., 2016). However, very few studies focused on the mineralogical and inorganic geochemical features of the coals in the basin (Morán, 1987; Hackley et al., 2005; Carruyo, 2017).

The minerals and concentrations of minor and trace elements are important for coal conversion and for evaluation of the paleo-depositional environment (Moore and Esmaeili, 2012; Dai et al., 2020a) by way of examples. Elements in coal appear to be in organic, inorganic and intimate organic associations (Dai et al, 2020b); while elemental concentrations are influenced by factors such as depositional environments of coal genesis, hydrothermal fluids, volcanic ash input, weathering or coalification processes (e.g., Dai et al., 2012). The element contents can also vary notably between

and even within coal seams (Yang et al., 2018). In this regard, mineralogy is useful in determining the modes of occurrence for trace elements. It is used in the correlation of coal seams, the identification of source areas, and the evaluation of environmental and health impacts during coal utilization (Ward, 2016). Statistical relationships between elements and ash yield are also frequently used to study their modes of occurrence (e.g., Qin et al., 2018; Dai et al., 2021).

Regarding the main source rocks at the time of peatification in the Guasare Coalfield, it was inferred that deltaic deposits of the Marcelina Formation were sourced from positive areas including the Guayana Shield (Parnaud et al., 1995). Also, Carruyo (2017) postulated that the source of minor, trace, and rare earth elements (REE) in Marcelina coals may have been partly sourced from granitoids such as the Late Triassic El Palmar Granite and El Carmen Granodiorite boulders (González de Juana et al., 1980), which outcrop at some places in the Perijá Range and the Andean region near the Colombia-Venezuela border and were likely exposed on the surface in the Paleocene (Van Der Lelij, 2013).

Moreover, the growing demand for energy has sparked global interest in the recovery of coalbed methane (CBM), a clean fossil fuel associated with broad coal deposits (Bustin and Clarkson, 1998). During the coalification processes, considerable amounts of hydrocarbons are generated and, partially, retained in the pore network (Petersen, 2006). Previous studies (Pan and Connell, 2012) have demonstrated that methane retention in the coal matrix can be explained by adsorption. Various factors such as coal petrography, coal rank, permeability, hydrodynamic setting, structure and burial history of the basin control CBM producibility (Scott, 2002; Chalmers et al., 2007; Solano-Acosta, 2007). Methane sorption capacity depends positively on total organic carbon (TOC) content, pore surface area, coal rank or fixed carbon, and inversely on maturity, mineral matter or moisture (Levy et al., 1997; Laxminarayana and Crosdale, 1999; Prinz and Littke, 2005). However,

positive trends exist between gas content (normalized to TOC) and illite content for dried coaly shale samples from SW Canada (Chalmers et al., 2008).

Numerous studies have been conducted on CBM potential of coal basins to improve our understanding of this unconventional energy resource (e.g., Mussa et al., 2021). With respect to the study area, Canónico (2002) and Tyler et al. (2006) estimated CBM resources to be 28-112 and 197-300 billion cubic meters, respectively, for this area on the basis of gas in-situ contents from United States coal (Eddy et al., 1982); since although profuse information is available on geology of coal seams in the Guasare Coalfield, data on gas content and gas distribution trends is very limited. Finally, most Guasare coal gas generation was attributed to thermogenic processes based on carbon isotope values (Berbesi et al., 2009; Quintero et al., 2011).

The main goals of this work are: (i) to characterize the mineralogical and elemental compositions of the mineral matter present in selected Marcelina coal seams (groups 2 to 11) intersected in cored boreholes; ii) to determine the distribution patterns of rare earth elements (REE) in the study coals for the first time; (iii) to investigate the provenance of trace and rare earth elements in coal samples from the Guasare Coalfield; (iv) to evaluate CBM potential of unmined and mineable coal seams at the Paso Diablo and Mina Norte open-pits, and (v) to investigate the role of the illite content with regard to reservoir gas capacity of Guasare coals. This information leads to assess in detail the distribution of the inorganic components in Marcelina coals at a mine-area and a basin-wide scale, and will prompt new exploration for CBM to evaluate its economic use in the study area.

2. Geological background

Geological features of the Sierra de Perijá have been described in literature (e.g., Kellogg, 1981; Audemard, 1991; Taboada et al., 2000; Duerto et al., 2006; Mann et al., 2006; Escalona and Mann,

2011). Uplift of the Sierra de Perijá started during the Oligocene and culminated in the Pliocene-Pleistocene (Kellogg, 1984). The Perijá Range is part of the Andean ridge, which is situated at the northwestern margin of Venezuela, specifically as a ramification towards the north of the Colombian Eastern Cordillera (Miller, 1962). Approximately at 9°N, a modification in trend from N20°W occurs, which is predominant in the northern Eastern Cordillera, to N25°E for the Perijá Range. The Sierra de Perijá remains at the northern edge of the Guajira Plains (latitude 11°10'N), constituting its crest the reference for the Colombia-Venezuela border (Fig. 1b). The main fractures related to the Sierra de Perijá's eastern flank include the Cuiba and Tigre left-lateral strike-slip faults (Bayona et al., 2011), which are oriented in the NE-SW direction and may have been formed along normal faults in the rifted Jurassic South America-African plate boundary (Lugo and Mann, 1995); as well as the El Palmar and Totumo faults with an orientation N-S, defining an abrupt uplift of the Sierra de Perijá, consecutive to that of the adjoining Lake Maracaibo Basin (Alvarado, 2007).

The Guasare Coal Basin and the Manuelote Syncline are structurally bound. This syncline can be defined as a NE-SW stretching tectonic horst, which is a known fold in the area under study and contains an axial plane that shares traits with the direction of the Tigre Fault (Pindell et al., 1998). The average value for total accumulated thickness of coal in the Marcelina Formation is 45-50 m, with scarce partings (González de Juana et al., 1980). This latter feature, along with low sulfur content and ash yield averaging 0.9 and 1.9 wt.% on a dry basis, respectively, are interpreted to be associated with the tectonic conditions ruling through the Paleocene in NW Venezuela; particularly by reason of low rates of subsidence (Hackley and Martínez, 2007). The stratigraphic succession in the Guasare Coalfield is composed of a series of sedimentary rocks of Phanerozoic age (see Fig. 3) overlying metamorphic basement (quartzites, amphibolites, and gneissoid schists being intruded by granite plutons) of the Precambrian Perijá Formation (Pérez et al., 2008). The lithology of the Marcelina Formation comprises sandy shales, black mudstones, grey sandstones, and coal horizons

(Sutton, 1946). At the bottom of the formation, the sandstones are thick, massive, light grey, and locally calcareous. The sandstones become finer upwards and appear to be interbedded with grey shales. Both sandstones and shales have lengthened nodules of blue-grey sandy limestone up to 3 m thick in the lower part of the formation (Escobar et al., 2011). The Marcelina Formation reflects a swamp paleo-depositional environment with similar peat accumulation and subsidence rates (McCabe, 1991), being formed by a deltaic sequence over the shelf edge of the Guasare Formation (González de Juana et al., 1980). In the area around the Paso Diablo mine, the Marcelina Formation conformably underlies the Misoa sands that represent a deltaic shoreface (Parnaud et al., 1995).

Figure 3

In the Paso Diablo mine, coal seams dip considerably ($8\text{-}12^\circ$) to the east; nevertheless, the dip is greater ($15^\circ\text{-}25^\circ$) towards the south and the seams appear to be nearly vertical (Hackley and Martínez, 2007). The structural geology in the Guasare Coalfield is governed by the El Tigre fault and by multiple minor faults oriented in a $N45^\circ W$ direction and spaced between 60 and 160 m (Alvarado, 2007). Towards the north, the coal seams gradually thin down to become lenses, while towards the south, the thickness of the seams increases. Coal seams are most common in the lower-central part of the Marcelina Formation (Fig. 2).

3. Samples and analytical procedures

Forty-six (46) coal core samples of 16 seams were collected from 16 drilled exploratory boreholes of the Marcelina Formation in the Paso Diablo mine and Mina Norte open-pit (Table 1 and Fig. 1c). About 3 kg of each whole seam sample were obtained from 2-4 individual samples. Then, the coal samples were homogenized using a Jones jaw crusher to obtain 100 g of each. We also provide previous unpublished proximate-ultimate data and gross calorific values (GCV) on additional 66 coals of 31 seams intersected in most wells under consideration (Carruyo, 2017; Tables 1 and 2). The location of the study seams in the stratigraphic column is shown in Figure 2.

Table 1

The coal samples were analyzed for moisture, ash yield, and volatile matter (VM) following the standards ISO 687:2010, ISO 1171:2010, and ISO 562:2010, respectively. The fixed carbon (FC) was calculated by subtracting the sum of these three parameters from the total (100 %). Ultimate analyses were also carried out using a LECO C-H-N 1000 apparatus in accordance with ISO 29541:2010 for C, H and N, and a LECO Truspec micro O analyser for direct O determination. Total sulfur was obtained by using a LECO SC32 apparatus according to ISO 19579:2006. TOC is calculated as the difference between the total carbon content and the inorganic carbon content. A LECO C-144 instrument was used to determine the total carbon content; while total inorganic carbon content was measured by using a CM5017 CO₂ coulometer. GCV values were determined through a Parr 6400 calorimeter following the norm ISO 1928:2009. Methane content of bulk crushed coal samples (50 mesh) was determined by a high-pressure volumetric sorption apparatus. Samples (100 mg) were air dried prior to methane sorption analysis. Each analysis was performed under isothermal conditions at 30°C and 6 MPa in order to compare samples. A value of 0.85 can be assumed to approximate the ratio of volumes of gas adsorbed on wet and dry coal (Kim, 1977). Reproducibility of the sorption analysis was within 3%.

The elemental compositions of raw (un-ashed) samples were obtained after the acid digestion of them following a two-step method devised to retain potentially volatile elements in solution (Querol et al., 1995). Al, Fe, P, Mg, Mn, Ca, Na, K, Ti, Zn, B, Sr, Ba, Cr, V, Ni and Pb were analyzed by inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-AES); while Li, Be, U, Co, Cu, Ga, Ge, As, Rb, Zr, Nb, Mo, Sb, Cs, W, Th, Se, Y, Sc and naturally-occurring lanthanides were analyzed by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). The international reference material SARM 19 was used to calculate the accuracy of the methods. The element results were treated using SPSS 22.0 package for Windows.

Mineralogical analysis of a subset (16) of core samples of an equal number of seams was performed by semi-quantitative X-ray diffraction (XRD) using a Bruker-AXS D8 Advance diffractometer equipped with a copper anode, CuK α radiation, tube conditions of 40 kV and 30 mA, $\Delta 2\theta=4-60^\circ$, step size = 0.03° , and time step = 0.1 s. The diffractograms were obtained using the powder technique. The organic carbon was removed from each coal sample by low-temperature oxygen-plasma ashing (LTA) through an IPC-4 chamber following the USGS method (Kolker et al., 2003). Semiquantitative mineralogical compositions (normalized to 100% ash) of coal samples were determined according to the procedure reported by Chung (1974). The clay fraction analyses of the LTA residues from selected coal samples were conducted separately. Such fraction ($< 2 \mu\text{m}$ effective diameter) of each LTA residue was isolated by ultrasonic dispersion in water treated with sodium hexametaphosphate, and further settling. Later, oriented-aggregate XRD technique was performed after treatment with ethylene glycol and heating to a maximum temperature of 550°C as routine treatments (Pope et al., 2001), to investigate the composition of the clay fractions.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Proximate and ultimate analyses

Table 2 displays values for ultimate and proximate analyses of the coal seams studied. The coals show low moisture contents (0.9-3.8 wt. % on a dry basis; averaging 2.0 wt. %) and are defined by low to medium ash yields between 0.7 and 9.9 wt. % on a dry basis (mean value of 3.0 wt. %). Fixed carbon and volatile matter range, respectively, from 49.0 to 61.6 wt. % on a dry basis (56.1 wt. % average) and from 36.6 to 48.1 wt. % on a dry ash-free basis (mean equals to 41.8 wt. %). In agreement with previous results (e.g., Carruyo, 2017), the measured gross calorific values for the coals (33.30-35.53 MJ/kg on a moist mineral-matter-free basis), along with proximate-ultimate data, denote that they have a rank of high volatile A bituminous following the ASTM D-388 classification. Also, the study coals exhibit low ($< 1\%$) to moderate (1-3%; Chou, 2012) contents of

total sulfur (0.33-1.56 wt. % on a dry basis; averaging 0.74 wt. %), which would indicate the accumulation of precursor organic matter in mostly telmatic depositional settings (Banerjee and Goodarzi, 1990) and an acidic pH during the peatification process (Bechtel et al., 2003). No regular variations in the proximate analysis data are observed either vertically or laterally.

Table 2

Carbon, oxygen, hydrogen, and nitrogen contents (dry basis) for the coals are, respectively, in the 79.66-87.47 wt. %, 6.56-8.56 wt. %, 4.93-5.93 wt. %, and 1.44-1.99 wt. % ranges (Table 2). Carbon and nitrogen contents fall into the high volatile bituminous range reported, but hydrogen and oxygen data are slightly higher and lower than the mean values indicated by Given (1984). O/C atomic ratios below 0.1 and H/C values around 0.8 agree with a high volatile bituminous A rank (Kopp et al., 2000). The study coals, particularly those of the lower Marcelina coal seams (groups 2 and 3), show relatively high H/C values compared to the majority of humic coals. These latter also have the highest volatile matter values (Table 2), thereby indicating that they are perhydrous coals, as previously stated by Escobar et al. (2016). Finally, the high relative proportions of carbon versus nitrogen for all the samples under consideration (Table 2) are typical of humic-type coals (Meyers and Ishiwatari, 1993).

4.2. Geochemistry of minor and trace elements

4.2.1. Element contents

Tables 3, 4, and 5 show the contents of a series of minor (0.01-1.0 wt%), trace (< 100 µg/g; Finkelman, 1993), and rare earth elements on a whole coal basis, as well as average values for world hard coals (Ketris and Yudovich, 2009) and Swaine's worldwide ranges (Swaine, 1990).

Table 3

Table 4

Table 5

The geochemical features of Marcelina coal seams do not vary regularly with depth. Similarly, nor were there significant differences in the element geochemistry of the Paso Diablo coals and those from Mina Norte. However, this latter finding is tentative because it is not supported statistically by enough data. Elemental concentrations in all the coal samples are near or below the lowest values in the Swaine's worldwide concentration ranges in coal (see Tables 3, 4, and 5). These low elemental contents may be explained by little input of detrital materials to domed-ombrogenous deposits protected from sediment influx during peat accumulation in the Guasare Coal Basin (Hackley and Martínez, 2007). Given the similar average ash yields for the Mina Norte (MN) and Paso Diablo (PD) coals (3.6 and 2.9 wt. %, respectively), when comparing elemental concentrations in both subsets of coals (see Tables 3, 4 and 5), results tentatively indicate that MN coals have in general slightly higher average trace element contents than PD coals; while these latter have higher or similar mean concentrations of Fe, Ca, Mg, K, and Na, but not of Al, than those. These features seem to agree with the slightly high contents of kaolinite found in Mina Norte coals with respect to those from Paso Diablo, as previously reported in literature (Hackley et al., 2005).

The coal samples show concentrations of B from 14.1 to 42.7 $\mu\text{g/g}$, suggesting that the study coals were formed in paleomires developed in freshwater habitats (Dai et al., 2020a), which is consistent with the low total sulfur content and the inferred ombrogenous mire depositional environment of the parent organic matter. However, the concentration of B in coal may be also influenced by factors such as hydrothermal fluids, volcanic activity, and acid waters (Karayiğit et al., 2017). For that reason, the B content can be used as paleosalinity indicator but it must be interpreted with caution. Further, relatively low Ni/Co ratios (mean of ~ 4) and high Ca/Sr values over 4 (Appendix) suggest an oxic-dysoxic depositional environment with no marine influence in the original peat mires where Marcelina coals were formed (Krejci-Graf, 1984; Rimmer, 2004). The total REE content (also named as REY when Y is included; Dai et al., 2016b) of the 46 coal samples ranges from 1.113 to

16.364 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (Appendix), with a mean value (4.578 $\mu\text{g/g}$) which is notably lower than the average REY in worldwide bituminous coal (68.6 $\mu\text{g/g}$; Yudovich and Ketris, 2006).

When comparing mean element concentrations in samples with average values for world hard coals (Ketris and Yudovich, 2009) by the use of concentration coefficients (CC = ratio of element concentration in sampled coals to average for world hard coals; Dai et al., 2016a), B, Ge, Se, and in some cases, Sb appear to be close to the averages for world hard coals ($0.5 < \text{CC} < 1$; Dai et al., 2015). The remaining elements analyzed and Cd (average for world hard coals equals 0.2 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and values < 0.01 $\mu\text{g/g}$ for samples; Hackley et al., 2005) are depleted ($\text{CC} < 0.5$) in the study coals. It has been also found that only F and Cl concentrations (89 and 380 $\mu\text{g/g}$) in Marcelina coals are higher than their respective average values (82 and 340 $\mu\text{g/g}$) for world hard coals (Morán, 1987).

4.2.2. Modes of occurrence of elements

Modes of occurrence of the elements in Marcelina coals were investigated using the Pearson correlation (r) between element contents and ash yield, although this statistical analysis should be used with caution (Dai et al., 2020b). Previous research works (e.g., Suárez-Ruiz et al., 2006) have established that elements whose concentration strongly follows the ash trend show a likely inorganic association, while organically-bound elements follow a completely opposite trend to the ash content. Only selenium seems to be mainly associated with the organic matter in sampled coals. The contents of a group of 22 minor, trace and rare earth elements (Table 6), show a weak correlation suggesting a mixed inorganic-organic association in the coal seams under consideration (Dai et al., 2021). The rest of the analyzed elements (Table 6) increases in samples parallel with ash content, which indicates a dominant affiliation with the mineral matter. No or weak correlation of several elements with ash yield may be explained by adsorption on coal surface, various modes of occurrence or anomalous low concentrations (Martínez et al., 2001). Further, positive correlations

of heavy (HREE, from Gd to Lu and Y) and light (LREE, from La to Eu) rare earth elements with Al, Ca, Fe, and P may reveal a terrigenous detrital origin for the REY species (Mishra et al., 2019). Lastly, the weak correlations ($-0.13 < r < +0.26$) between total sulfur and other elements analyzed, and no relationship between total sulfur and ash yield, reflect the mainly organic affiliation of sulfur in Marcelina coals (Hackley et al., 2005; Hackley and Martínez, 2007).

Table 6

Multivariate clustering based on elemental contents was carried out in order to identify the similarity of elements in the study coals and to group those into clusters. In coal geochemistry, this statistical tool has been usually applied in different fields such as the development of neural models to estimate moisture and ash content in coals and coaly shales (Ghosh et al., 2016) or the mode of occurrence of the trace elements in coals (Xu et al., 2021). However, it is necessary to ensure the compositional homogeneity in the dataset (Eskenezy et al., 2010). Cluster analysis was performed following the Ward's method (Everitt, 1993), and similarity percent was obtained after calculating square Euclidean distances (cut-off of 900; Fig. 4). Three groups of elements were determined. The first is wide and includes at least 12 elements within this association. Detailed analysis of these elements suggests three subgroups having a geochemical significance: Na–B and Mn–Ba–Sr, respectively, may be associated with groundwater movement and carbonate minerals (Beaton et al., 1991); while the third is made up of P, V, Zr, Li, Cu, Ni, and Cr, and these seem to be related to primary paleoproductivity and particular paleoredox conditions (Rimmer, 2004). The second group (Fe, Al, Cs, Ca, and Mg, among others) reveals a predominant clay mineral affiliation (Cullers, 1994) and, to a lesser extent, both carbonate and other possible associations. The last group includes some redox-sensitive trace elements (Mo, Rb, Nb, Co, U, Th, As, Be, and Sb; Cullers, 2002), along with another subgroup of elements (Zn, Pb, Ga, Ge, La, S, Sc, and REY) bound in sulfides, sand-forming minerals, and heavy detrital species (Ward, 2016).

Figure 4

4.2.3. Sediment source of elements

In an attempt to identify the source of trace elements in the coals under study, and considering the positive Pearson correlations between Al (Fralick and Kronberg, 1997) and trace elements such as Cr, Co, Th, Sc, La and REEs, which confirms the relative immobility of these lithophile elements (Yan et al., 2006), we can use here these latter elements to investigate the detrital input during peat accumulation in the Guasare Coalfield. In detail, the concentrations of La and Th (enriched in felsic sources) as well as Co and Sc (suggestive of mafic) may allow distinguishing between mafic and felsic provenance (e.g., Cullers, 2002). As shown in Table 7, when comparing La/Sc, Th/Sc, La/Co, and Th/Cr values of Marcelina coals with the ratios of sediments sourced from mafic and felsic rocks (Cullers et al., 1988; Cullers, 2000; Cullers and Podkovyrov, 2000), most samples lay within or closer to the felsic ranges, suggesting a probable granitic or metamorphic felsic nature of the source rocks. The La-Sc-Th ternary diagram can also give information about the provenance characteristics (Cullers, 2002). In this diagram, the average compositions of andesite and basalt (Condie, 1993), as well as some nearby granitoids (El Carmen Granodiorite and El Palmar Granite boulders; Van Der Lelij, 2013), are used for comparison purposes. The majority of samples plot near granitoid compositions (Fig. 5), which indicates that mineral fractions in Marcelina coals were derived presumably by the influence of felsic contribution.

Table 7

Figure 5

The REE distribution pattern in the sedimentary rocks is a very useful tool to unravel the provenance (Taylor and McLennan, 1985). In this regard, to identify a possible igneous source rock, the REE data of Marcelina coals are normalized relative to the chondrite values (Boynnton, 1984) and compared with granitic rocks from areas located close to the mines under study. The subscript “*n*” indicates C1- or chondrite-normalized abundances. Typical REE patterns of the Paso Diablo and Mina Norte coal samples are shown in Figure 6. They are significantly similar to each

other and those of the El Palmar Granite and El Carmen Granodiorite boulders in the foothills of the Sierra of Perijá (Van Der Lelij, 2013). The chondrite-normalized patterns of samples from both mines are characterized by a quite flat HREE shape, LREE being nearly three times higher than HREE on average and $Eu_n/Eu^* < 1$ (see Fig. 6 and Appendix A), which agree with felsic sources (e.g., granites, gneisses, and pegmatites) with clear negative Eu anomaly (Armstrong-Altrin et al., 2004), rather than Eu mobility favored by reducing and low temperature conditions during peat accumulation (Eskenazy, 1987). By contrast, granodiorite often shows a positive Eu anomaly (Cullers, 1994). Slightly negative Ce anomalies also support a felsic provenance, although other alternatives to account for a negative Ce anomaly (Ce immobility, in-situ precipitation, and Ce^{+3} to Ce^{+4} oxidation) cannot be fully ruled out (Dai et al., 2016b). Finally, coal samples show Gd_n/Yb_n and Eu_n/Eu^* ratios below 2 and not exceeding 0.85, respectively (Appendix A), which is consistent with K-feldspar-rich granitic source rocks of Cambrian age or younger (McLennan, 1989; Taylor and McLennan, 1985).

Figure 6

4.3. Mineralogy

The mineralogy of the study coal seams is quite uniform (Table 8). Quartz and kaolinite are the predominant mineral species in the low temperature ash of the samples. Although these primary minerals are usually detrital in nature (Karayiğit et al., 2018), their occurrence in the coal samples could also result from authigenic precipitation in the raised peat mires protected from clastic inflow at the time of peatification (Ward, 2016). This would be consistent with a progradational deltaic environment for the Marcelina coals (Hackley and Martínez, 2007). A series of secondary minerals identified in the coal samples include illite, K-feldspar, sphalerite, pyrite, plagioclase, diaspore, hematite, and apatite, among others; which are also present in small proportions (see Table 8).

Table 8

Traces of bassanite were also detected in the LTA residues. Although Ca sulfates may represent either authigenic sediments or crystallization of ions from aqueous solution in the coal pore structure with evaporation, they were probably formed during the LTA process (Koukouzas et al., 2010). Butlerite and whewellite are rare minerals in coals and they are, respectively, a product of oxidation of pyrite (Kruszewski, 2013) and the result of an authigenic accumulation of Ca oxalate in coal seams (Echigo and Kimata, 2010). Carbonate minerals consist of small quantities of ankerite and siderite, which are the dominant iron-bearing species in coals when pyrite is absent or found in very low amounts (Ward et al., 2001), and they both would have been authigenically precipitated within mires in early diagenetic stages into the Paleocene (Ward et al. 1996), which is agreement with the freshwater conditions in which the study coals were formed (Hackley and Martínez, 2007). Oriented-aggregate XRD analysis indicated that kaolinite is the dominant component of the clay fraction of the study coals, and that illite and other clay minerals are usually present in minor and trace amounts, respectively. The predominance of kaolinite over the other minerals in the clay fraction, along with presence of whewellite and bassanite in the LTA materials, agree with a low detrital input to the paleomire and a significant portion of Ca associated to organic macerals (Koukouzas et al., 2010). Differences in illite contents in our samples can reveal subtle changes in provenance and depositional setting (Escobar et al., 2016).

4.4. Coalbed methane in the Marcelina seams

4.4.1. Numerical modeling of gas generated by Guasare coals

Generation of methane during coalification is modeled by calculating the amounts of volatiles in view of the atomic H/C and O/C ratios at the beginning of the high-volatile bituminous rank (0.85 and 0.13; Kopp et al., 2000) and averages of both ratios for Guasare coals (0.78 and 0.066). More exactly, complex organic “molecules” break down, releasing volatiles, and are gradually converted to hard coal and finally graphite, with decreasing atomic H/C and O/C ratios down to near zero

(Suggate, 2002). Only methane, carbon dioxide and water molecules were considered in order to simplify the modeling process. Other assumptions of the model are: methane is not significantly generated during early stages of coalification (Kopp et al., 2000) and the fact that the ratio of carbon dioxide to methane as gases released from organic matter is assumed to be 2 at maturity levels (~0.75%) of high-volatile bituminous A Guasare coals (Kopp et al., 2000; Escobar et al., 2016).

Once the numerical analysis described by Kopp and Bennett (2001) was carried out (Appendix B), we also assumed a mass loss of around 33% during the transition from lignite to high-volatile bituminous A coal (Tang et al., 1996). The model has predicted a methane generative potential of ~11 cm³ per gram of raw coal and CBM reserves in the Guasare Coalfield near 17.6 billion m³.

4.4.2. Methane sorption capacity of Guasare coals

Table 2 shows the values for gas volume per unit weight of each sampled coal seam (G_c). High pressure desorption data from dried coal samples indicated methane sorption capacity data ranging from 5.87 to 13.0 cm³/g, approaching the economic threshold of 9.30 cm³/g (Tang et al., 1996). These results were slightly lower than the dry, ash-free coalbed gas contents (G_{daf}) estimated theoretically by an indirect method from seam depth and proximate data (1.60-16.4 cm³/g; Juliao, 2010), which reveals that Guasare coals could accommodate more gas than it would be present in them. Experimental data are also coherent with methane storage capacities (3.42-13.0 cm³/g) of raw Guasare coals reported by Tyler et al. (2006), thereby suggesting that Marcelina seams can be considered to contain notable amounts of coal-bed methane.

The gas content values (G_c) for the Guasare Coalfield represents only the total volume of gas that is adsorbed by van der Waals forces to coal's interior surface area, but not to gas retention in other forms such as free gas present in the open pore spaces of coal and within natural cleats and

fractures, dissolved in formation water, and trapped gas within the matrix porosity (Clarkson and Bustin, 1996). Our results tend to underestimate the methane sorption capacity of Guasare coals due to gas loss after sampling and during crushing of samples. Hence, according to Strapóć et al. (2007), the measured gas content is equivalent to the residual gas fraction and to a part of the desorbed gas.

4.4.3. Clay content and CBM accumulation

Among the few studies have been carried out on the role of clays in methane sorption capacity of coal, Lu et al. (1995) indicated that illite is able to sorb methane at pressures from 1 to 7 MPa. Knowing that moisture in coal reduces the ability of the clay fraction to retain methane because moisture occupies sorption sites within the clays (Chalmers et al., 2008), total clay and illite contents are plotted versus the gas content on 16 dried samples (Fig. 7) in order to evaluate possible secondary influences of both variables on methane sorption capacity. Normalized data are presented on a per unit TOC volume basis assuming that the density of kerogen remains constant.

Figure 7

Negligible trend exists between gas content normalized to TOC and total clay content (Fig. 7a), in contrast to the positive relationship between methane sorption capacity normalized to TOC and illite content considering a sufficiently broad range (0.5-5%) of the latter variable (Fig. 7b), reflecting the notion that kaolinite and quartz have low sorption capacity compared to illite and the positive relationship of the latter clay with the surface area (Chalmers et al., 2008).

5. Conclusions

The high volatile bituminous A coals of the Guasare Coalfield contain low proportions of mineral matter and show no regular vertical and lateral variation in mineralogy and inorganic geochemistry. Kaolinite and quartz are the dominant mineral phases in selected Marcelina coal seams. In general, mean values of trace element concentrations in Marcelina coals generally indicate strong depletion

compared to the averages for world hard coals. Although this latter geochemical characteristic can make difficult a reliable statistical analysis to elucidate the modes of occurrence of elements, they all (except Se) show inorganic affinity or intermediate association and mixed mode of occurrence.

Regarding the provenance of trace and rare earth elements in Marcelina coals, Th/Sc, Th/Co, Th/Cr, La/Sc, LREE enrichment, and clear negative Eu anomalies reveal the predominant felsic character of the source rocks. Similarly, La-Th-Sc values and low Eu_n/Eu^* ratios are in agreement with Phanerozoic granitoids and their metamorphic equivalents as source rocks. Lastly, although a sediment contribution from metamorphic rocks of the Perijá Formation and other possibilities (as la Luna carbonate rocks and relatively nearby La Quinta mafic volcanoclastic materials; see Haze, 1984) cannot be completely dismissed, the comparison of REE patterns and Eu anomalies to the source rocks suggests that the mineral matter in Marcelina coals was, in part, a result of detrital input derived from granitoids such as the El Palmar Granite and El Carmen Granodiorite boulders or other similar granitic rocks. Data from raw Guasare coals indicates that methane contents range from 5 to 11 cm^3/g , values similar to that obtained from the numerical model (near 11 cm^3/g). Finally, the illite content showed a positive relationship with gas storage capacity when this latter is normalized to TOC on dried coal samples.

CRedit author statement

Gonzalo Márquez: Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft, Investigation, Supervision;

Manuel Martínez: Writing - Review & Editing, Formal analysis, Validation; **Gabriela Carruyo:**

Visualization, Investigation; **Carlos Boente:** Writing - Review & Editing, Formal analysis; **Erika**

Lorenzo: Investigation, Data curation; **Rafael Tocco:** Writing - Review & Editing, Resources.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. There are no conflicts of interest to declare.

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Figure 1: a) and b), respectively, maps showing the location of the Guasare Coalfield in NW Venezuela and the Paso Diablo and open-pit mines in this basin (modified from Escobar et al., 2016); c) situation of exploratory boreholes.

Figure 2: Stratigraphic units in the Sierra of Perijá (modified from Escobar et al., 2016).

Figure 3: Lithologic column of the Paso Diablo and Mina Norte open-cut mines showing coal seam names and stratigraphic position of coal samples (modified from Quintero et al., 2011).

Figure 4: Dendrogram showing correlation of elements in the Marcelina coal seams.

Figure 5: La-Sc-Th triangular diagram for the coals under study. Data from local granitoids (El Palmar Granite and El Carmen Granodiorite; Van Der Lelij, 2013) are included.

Figure 6: Chondrite-normalized REE plots for the Guasare coals, El Palmar and El Carmen granitoids.

Figure 7: Plots of gas content normalized to per-unit TOC on a dried basis with the total clay (a) and illite (b) contents.

Elemental composition and mineralogy of NW Venezuelan Guasare coals: Provenance study and role of illite in methane sorption capacity

G. MÁRQUEZ^{a,*}, M. MARTÍNEZ^b, G. CARRUYO^c, C. BOENTE^a, E. LORENZO^d and R. TOCCO^e

^a Center for Research in Sustainable Chemistry (CIQSO), University of Huelva, 21006 Huelva, Spain

^b Institute of Earth Sciences, Faculty of Sciences, Central University of Venezuela, Caracas 3895-1010A, Venezuela

^c School of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, University of Zulia, Maracaibo 4002-A, Venezuela

^d School of Engineering Sciences, State University Santa Elena Peninsula, 240204 La Libertad, Ecuador

^e Independent Petroleum Geochemistry Consultant, Madrid, 28410, Spain

Abstract: A series of coal seams (groups 4 to 11) of Paleocene age in the Marcelina Formation have been open pit exploited in two mines (Paso Diablo and Mina Norte) in the Guasare Coalfield (NW Venezuela). An investigation has been conducted on the elemental composition, mineralogy, and coalbed methane (CBM) in Guasare coals. For this study, 46 core coal samples of 16 seams (groups 2 to 7) were collected from 16 exploratory boreholes that were drilled in both mines. It was also considered unpublished proximate-ultimate and gross calorific data of other 66 coals of 31 seams intersected in most of these wells. The coals under study showed low ash yields (3.4 wt. % on average) and were classified as high volatile bituminous A. Mean values of trace element and lanthanide (REE) contents in Marcelina coals generally indicate depletion compared to average values for world hard coals. The statistical evaluations indicate that elements (except Se) show inorganic affinity or intermediate association and mixed mode of occurrence. La/Sc, Th/Sc, La/Co, and Th/Cr ratios support a felsic or metamorphic felsic source for the mineral matter present in Marcelina coals. Most coal samples exhibited similar normalized REE patterns, showing light REE enriched, as well as negative Ce and Eu anomalies. The comparison of REE patterns to those of some nearby granitoids suggests that Marcelina coals received a supply of sediments from these granitic source rocks. The mineralogical compositions of representative coal samples are notably similar, kaolinite and quartz were noted as the major mineral species in all coal seams. The measured gas volumes available for CBM production from Marcelina seams vary approximately between 5 and 11 cm³/g. Variation in the illite content has an appreciable positive effect on gas adsorption capacity of Guasare coals. Lastly, a numerical model of the gas generative potential of the coals in the Marcelina Formation was also developed.

Key-words: bituminous coal, Guasare Coalfield, elemental composition, mineralogy, CBM, illite content.

1. Introduction

Venezuela hosts potential resources of approximately ten billion metric tons of coal, 80 percent of them located in the Paleocene aged Guasare Coalfield (e.g., Carruyo, 2017). This basin stretches over a relatively small (55×5 km) geographical zone in the NW sector of Zulia State (Fig. 1a), 85 km northwest of the city of Maracaibo (Escobar et al., 1997). The Guasare Coalfield contains the majority (~1.6 billion tons) of the Venezuelan bituminous coal reserves and holds about 30 coal

seams in the Paleocene Marcelina Formation, with good lateral continuity and thicknesses ranging from 2 to 13 m (Quintero et al., 2011; Escobar et al., 2016). The Marcelina coal seams have been exploited in two mines (Paso Diablo and Mina Norte), operated by open-cast methods, since 1987 (Carruyo, 2017). The Paso Diablo mine and the nearby Mina Norte open-pit are located in the eastern flank of the Sierra de Perijá, between the Oca Fault northwards and the Totumo-Inciarte uplift southwards (Fig. 1b). According to Hackley and Martínez (2007), coal seams in both mines are classified into 11 groups (numbered from bottom to top; see Fig. 2) which, in turn, have been divided into seams so that the stratigraphically highest bed is assigned a Latin capital letter and each of the next lower seams are given letters farther down along the alphabet.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Previous geological studies have been conducted on the mineable and unmined Marcelina coal seams (e.g., [Martínez et al., 1989](#); [Juliao, 2010](#)). The Guasare Coalfield has been studied in terms of coal-bed methane potential (Canónico, 2002; Tyler et al., 2006), petrography (Hackley and Martínez, 2007; Escobar et al., 2016), palynology (Pardo, 2004; Petersen et al., 2009), and organic geochemistry (Canónico et al., 2004; [Quintero et al., 2011](#); [Escobar et al., 2016](#)). However, very few studies focused on the mineralogical and inorganic geochemical features of the coals in the basin (Morán, 1987; Hackley et al., 2005; Carruyo, 2017).

The minerals and concentrations of minor and trace elements are important for coal conversion and for evaluation of the paleo-depositional environment (Moore and Esmacili, 2012; Dai et al., 2020a) by way of examples. Elements in coal appear to be in organic, inorganic and intimate organic associations (Dai et al, 2020b); while elemental concentrations are influenced by factors such as depositional environments of coal genesis, hydrothermal fluids, volcanic ash input, weathering or coalification processes (e.g., Dai et al., 2012). The element contents can also vary notably between

and even within coal seams (Yang et al., 2018). In this regard, mineralogy is useful in determining the modes of occurrence for trace elements. It is used in the correlation of coal seams, the identification of source areas, and the evaluation of environmental and health impacts during coal utilization (Ward, 2016). Statistical relationships between elements and ash yield are also frequently used to study their modes of occurrence (e.g., Qin et al., 2018; Dai et al., 2021).

Regarding the main source rocks at the time of peatification in the Guasare Coalfield, it was inferred that deltaic deposits of the Marcelina Formation were sourced from positive areas including the Guayana Shield (Parnaud et al., 1995). Also, Carruyo (2017) postulated that the source of minor, trace, and rare earth elements (REE) in Marcelina coals may have been partly sourced from granitoids such as the Late Triassic El Palmar Granite and El Carmen Granodiorite boulders (González de Juana et al., 1980), which outcrop at some places in the Perijá Range and the Andean region near the Colombia-Venezuela border and were likely exposed on the surface in the Paleocene (Van Der Lelij, 2013).

Moreover, the growing demand for energy has sparked global interest in the recovery of coalbed methane (CBM), a clean fossil fuel associated with broad coal deposits (Bustin and Clarkson, 1998). During the coalification processes, considerable amounts of hydrocarbons are generated and, partially, retained in the pore network (Petersen, 2006). Previous studies (Pan and Connell, 2012) have demonstrated that methane retention in the coal matrix can be explained by adsorption. Various factors such as coal petrography, coal rank, permeability, hydrodynamic setting, structure and burial history of the basin control CBM producibility (Scott, 2002; Chalmers et al., 2007; Solano-Acosta, 2007). Methane sorption capacity depends positively on total organic carbon (TOC) content, pore surface area, coal rank or fixed carbon, and inversely on maturity, mineral matter or moisture (Levy et al., 1997; Laxminarayana and Crosdale, 1999; Prinz and Littke, 2005). However,

positive trends exist between gas content (normalized to TOC) and illite content for dried coaly shale samples from SW Canada (Chalmers et al., 2008).

Numerous studies have been conducted on CBM potential of coal basins to improve our understanding of this unconventional energy resource (e.g., Mussa et al., 2021). With respect to the study area, Canónico (2002) and Tyler et al. (2006) estimated CBM resources to be 28-112 and 197-300 billion cubic meters, respectively, for this area on the basis of gas in-situ contents from United States coal (Eddy et al., 1982); since although profuse information is available on geology of coal seams in the Guasare Coalfield, data on gas content and gas distribution trends is very limited. Finally, most Guasare coal gas generation was attributed to thermogenic processes based on carbon isotope values (Berbesi et al., 2009; Quintero et al., 2011).

The main goals of this work are: (i) to characterize the mineralogical and elemental compositions of the mineral matter present in selected Marcelina coal seams (groups 2 to 11) intersected in cored boreholes; ii) to determine the distribution patterns of rare earth elements (REE) in the study coals for the first time; (iii) to investigate the provenance of trace and rare earth elements in coal samples from the Guasare Coalfield; (iv) to evaluate CBM potential of unmined and mineable coal seams at the Paso Diablo and Mina Norte open-pits, and (v) to investigate the role of the illite content with regard to reservoir gas capacity of Guasare coals. This information leads to assess in detail the distribution of the inorganic components in Marcelina coals at a mine-area and a basin-wide scale, and will prompt new exploration for CBM to evaluate its economic use in the study area.

2. Geological background

Geological features of the Sierra de Perijá have been described in literature (e.g., Kellogg, 1981; Audemard, 1991; Taboada et al., 2000; Duerto et al., 2006; Mann et al., 2006; Escalona and Mann,

2011). Uplift of the Sierra de Perijá started during the Oligocene and culminated in the Pliocene-Pleistocene (Kellogg, 1984). The Perijá Range is part of the Andean ridge, which is situated at the northwestern margin of Venezuela, specifically as a ramification towards the north of the Colombian Eastern Cordillera (Miller, 1962). Approximately at 9°N, a modification in trend from N20°W occurs, which is predominant in the northern Eastern Cordillera, to N25°E for the Perijá Range. The Sierra de Perijá remains at the northern edge of the Guajira Plains (latitude 11°10'N), constituting its crest the reference for the Colombia-Venezuela border (Fig. 1b). The main fractures related to the Sierra de Perijá's eastern flank include the Cuiba and Tigre left-lateral strike-slip faults (Bayona et al., 2011), which are oriented in the NE-SW direction and may have been formed along normal faults in the rifted Jurassic South America-African plate boundary (Lugo and Mann, 1995); as well as the El Palmar and Totumo faults with an orientation N-S, defining an abrupt uplift of the Sierra de Perijá, consecutive to that of the adjoining Lake Maracaibo Basin (Alvarado, 2007).

The Guasare Coal Basin and the Manuelote Syncline are structurally bound. This syncline can be defined as a NE-SW stretching tectonic horst, which is a known fold in the area under study and contains an axial plane that shares traits with the direction of the Tigre Fault (Pindell et al., 1998). The average value for total accumulated thickness of coal in the Marcelina Formation is 45-50 m, with scarce partings (González de Juana et al., 1980). This latter feature, along with low sulfur content and ash yield averaging 0.9 and 1.9 wt.% on a dry basis, respectively, are interpreted to be associated with the tectonic conditions ruling through the Paleocene in NW Venezuela; particularly by reason of low rates of subsidence (Hackley and Martínez, 2007). The stratigraphic succession in the Guasare Coalfield is composed of a series of sedimentary rocks of Phanerozoic age (see Fig. 3) overlying metamorphic basement (quartzites, amphibolites, and gneissoid schists being intruded by granite plutons) of the Precambrian Perijá Formation (Pérez et al., 2008). The lithology of the Marcelina Formation comprises sandy shales, black mudstones, grey sandstones, and coal horizons

(Sutton, 1946). At the bottom of the formation, the sandstones are thick, massive, light grey, and locally calcareous. The sandstones become finer upwards and appear to be interbedded with grey shales. Both sandstones and shales have lengthened nodules of blue-grey sandy limestone up to 3 m thick in the lower part of the formation (Escobar et al., 2011). The Marcelina Formation reflects a swamp paleo-depositional environment with similar peat accumulation and subsidence rates (McCabe, 1991), being formed by a deltaic sequence over the shelf edge of the Guasare Formation (González de Juana et al., 1980). In the area around the Paso Diablo mine, the Marcelina Formation conformably underlies the Misoa sands that represent a deltaic shoreface (Parnaud et al., 1995).

Figure 3

In the Paso Diablo mine, coal seams dip considerably (8-12°) to the east; nevertheless, the dip is greater (15°-25°) towards the south and the seams appear to be nearly vertical (Hackley and Martínez, 2007). The structural geology in the Guasare Coalfield is governed by the El Tigre fault and by multiple minor faults oriented in a N45°W direction and spaced between 60 and 160 m (Alvarado, 2007). Towards the north, the coal seams gradually thin down to become lenses, while towards the south, the thickness of the seams increases. Coal seams are most common in the lower-central part of the Marcelina Formation (Fig. 2).

3. Samples and analytical procedures

Forty-six (46) coal core samples of 16 seams were collected from 16 drilled exploratory boreholes of the Marcelina Formation in the Paso Diablo mine and Mina Norte open-pit (Table 1 and Fig. 1c). About 3 kg of each whole seam sample were obtained from 2-4 individual samples. Then, the coal samples were homogenized using a Jones jaw crusher to obtain 100 g of each. We also provide previous unpublished proximate-ultimate data and gross calorific values (GCV) on additional 66 coals of 31 seams intersected in most wells under consideration (Carruyo, 2017; Tables 1 and 2). The location of the study seams in the stratigraphic column is shown in Figure 2.

Table 1

The coal samples were analyzed for moisture, ash yield, and volatile matter (VM) following the standards ISO 687:2010, ISO 1171:2010, and ISO 562:2010, respectively. The fixed carbon (FC) was calculated by subtracting the sum of these three parameters from the total (100 %). Ultimate analyses were also carried out using a LECO C-H-N 1000 apparatus in accordance with ISO 29541:2010 for C, H and N, and a LECO Truspec micro O analyser for direct O determination. Total sulfur was obtained by using a LECO SC32 apparatus according to ISO 19579:2006. TOC is calculated as the difference between the total carbon content and the inorganic carbon content. A LECO C-144 instrument was used to determine the total carbon content; while total inorganic carbon content was measured by using a CM5017 CO₂ coulometer. GCV values were determined through a Parr 6400 calorimeter following the norm ISO 1928:2009. Methane content of bulk crushed coal samples (50 mesh) was determined by a high-pressure volumetric sorption apparatus. Samples (100 mg) were air dried prior to methane sorption analysis. Each analysis was performed under isothermal conditions at 30°C and 6 MPa in order to compare samples. A value of 0.85 can be assumed to approximate the ratio of volumes of gas adsorbed on wet and dry coal (Kim, 1977). Reproducibility of the sorption analysis was within 3%.

The elemental compositions of raw (un-ashed) samples were obtained after the acid digestion of them following a two-step method devised to retain potentially volatile elements in solution (Querol et al., 1995). Al, Fe, P, Mg, Mn, Ca, Na, K, Ti, Zn, B, Sr, Ba, Cr, V, Ni and Pb were analyzed by inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-AES); while Li, Be, U, Co, Cu, Ga, Ge, As, Rb, Zr, Nb, Mo, Sb, Cs, W, Th, Se, Y, Sc and naturally-occurring lanthanides were analyzed by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). The international reference material SARM 19 was used to calculate the accuracy of the methods. The element results were treated using SPSS 22.0 package for Windows.

Mineralogical analysis of a subset (16) of core samples of an equal number of seams was performed by semi-quantitative X-ray diffraction (XRD) using a Bruker-AXS D8 Advance diffractometer equipped with a copper anode, CuK α radiation, tube conditions of 40 kV and 30 mA, $\Delta 2\theta=4-60^\circ$, step size = 0.03° , and time step = 0.1 s. The diffractograms were obtained using the powder technique. The organic carbon was removed from each coal sample by low-temperature oxygen-plasma ashing (LTA) through an IPC-4 chamber following the USGS method (Kolker et al., 2003). Semiquantitative mineralogical compositions (normalized to 100% ash) of coal samples were determined according to the procedure reported by Chung (1974). The clay fraction analyses of the LTA residues from selected coal samples were conducted separately. Such fraction ($< 2 \mu\text{m}$ effective diameter) of each LTA residue was isolated by ultrasonic dispersion in water treated with sodium hexametaphosphate, and further settling. Later, oriented-aggregate XRD technique was performed after treatment with ethylene glycol and heating to a maximum temperature of 550°C as routine treatments (Pope et al., 2001), to investigate the composition of the clay fractions.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Proximate and ultimate analyses

Table 2 displays values for ultimate and proximate analyses of the coal seams studied. The coals show low moisture contents (0.9-3.8 wt. % on a dry basis; averaging 2.0 wt. %) and are defined by low to medium ash yields between 0.7 and 9.9 wt. % on a dry basis (mean value of 3.0 wt. %). Fixed carbon and volatile matter range, respectively, from 49.0 to 61.6 wt. % on a dry basis (56.1 wt. % average) and from 36.6 to 48.1 wt. % on a dry ash-free basis (mean equals to 41.8 wt. %). In agreement with previous results (e.g., Carruyo, 2017), the measured gross calorific values for the coals (33.30-35.53 MJ/kg on a moist mineral-matter-free basis), along with proximate-ultimate data, denote that they have a rank of high volatile A bituminous following the ASTM D-388 classification. Also, the study coals exhibit low ($< 1\%$) to moderate (1-3%; Chou, 2012) contents of

total sulfur (0.33-1.56 wt. % on a dry basis; averaging 0.74 wt. %), which would indicate the accumulation of precursor organic matter in mostly telmatic depositional settings (Banerjee and Goodarzi, 1990) and an acidic pH during the peatification process (Bechtel et al., 2003). No regular variations in the proximate analysis data are observed either vertically or laterally.

Table 2

Carbon, oxygen, hydrogen, and nitrogen contents (dry basis) for the coals are, respectively, in the 79.66-87.47 wt. %, 6.56-8.56 wt. %, 4.93-5.93 wt. %, and 1.44-1.99 wt. % ranges (Table 2). Carbon and nitrogen contents fall into the high volatile bituminous range reported, but hydrogen and oxygen data are slightly higher and lower than the mean values indicated by Given (1984). O/C atomic ratios below 0.1 and H/C values around 0.8 agree with a high volatile bituminous A rank (Kopp et al., 2000). The study coals, particularly those of the lower Marcelina coal seams (groups 2 and 3), show relatively high H/C values compared to the majority of humic coals. These latter also have the highest volatile matter values (Table 2), thereby indicating that they are perhydrous coals, as previously stated by Escobar et al. (2016). Finally, the high relative proportions of carbon versus nitrogen for all the samples under consideration (Table 2) are typical of humic-type coals (Meyers and Ishiwatari, 1993).

4.2. Geochemistry of minor and trace elements

4.2.1. Element contents

Tables 3, 4, and 5 show the contents of a series of minor (0.01-1.0 wt%), trace (< 100 µg/g; Finkelman, 1993), and rare earth elements on a whole coal basis, as well as average values for world hard coals (Ketris and Yudovich, 2009) and Swaine's worldwide ranges (Swaine, 1990).

Table 3

Table 4

Table 5

The geochemical features of Marcelina coal seams do not vary regularly with depth. Similarly, nor were there significant differences in the element geochemistry of the Paso Diablo coals and those from Mina Norte. However, this latter finding is tentative because it is not supported statistically by enough data. Elemental concentrations in all the coal samples are near or below the lowest values in the Swaine's worldwide concentration ranges in coal (see Tables 3, 4, and 5). These low elemental contents may be explained by little input of detrital materials to domed-ombrogenous deposits protected from sediment influx during peat accumulation in the Guasare Coal Basin (Hackley and Martínez, 2007). Given the similar average ash yields for the Mina Norte (MN) and Paso Diablo (PD) coals (3.6 and 2.9 wt. %, respectively), when comparing elemental concentrations in both subsets of coals (see Tables 3, 4 and 5), results tentatively indicate that MN coals have in general slightly higher average trace element contents than PD coals; while these latter have higher or similar mean concentrations of Fe, Ca, Mg, K, and Na, but not of Al, than those. These features seem to agree with the slightly high contents of kaolinite found in Mina Norte coals with respect to those from Paso Diablo, as previously reported in literature (Hackley et al., 2005).

The coal samples show concentrations of B from 14.1 to 42.7 µg/g, suggesting that the study coals were formed in paleomires developed in freshwater habitats (Dai et al., 2020a), which is consistent with the low total sulfur content and the inferred ombrogenous mire depositional environment of the parent organic matter. However, the concentration of B in coal may be also influenced by factors such as hydrothermal fluids, volcanic activity, and acid waters (Karayiğit et al., 2017). For that reason, the B content can be used as paleosalinity indicator but it must be interpreted with caution. Further, relatively low Ni/Co ratios (mean of ~4) and high Ca/Sr values over 4 (Appendix) suggest an oxic-dysoxic depositional environment with no marine influence in the original peat mires where Marcelina coals were formed (Krejci-Graf, 1984; Rimmer, 2004). The total REE content (also named as REY when Y is included; Dai et al., 2016b) of the 46 coal samples ranges from 1.113 to

16.364 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (Appendix), with a mean value (4.578 $\mu\text{g/g}$) which is notably lower than the average REY in worldwide bituminous coal (68.6 $\mu\text{g/g}$; Yudovich and Ketris, 2006).

When comparing mean element concentrations in samples with average values for world hard coals (Ketris and Yudovich, 2009) by the use of concentration coefficients (CC = ratio of element concentration in sampled coals to average for world hard coals; Dai et al., 2016a), B, Ge, Se, and in some cases, Sb appear to be close to the averages for world hard coals ($0.5 < \text{CC} < 1$; Dai et al., 2015). The remaining elements analyzed and Cd (average for world hard coals equals 0.2 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and values $< 0.01 \mu\text{g/g}$ for samples; Hackley et al., 2005) are depleted ($\text{CC} < 0.5$) in the study coals. It has been also found that only F and Cl concentrations (89 and 380 $\mu\text{g/g}$) in Marcelina coals are higher than their respective average values (82 and 340 $\mu\text{g/g}$) for world hard coals (Morán, 1987).

4.2.2. Modes of occurrence of elements

Modes of occurrence of the elements in Marcelina coals were investigated using the Pearson correlation (r) between element contents and ash yield, although this statistical analysis should be used with caution (Dai et al., 2020b). Previous research works (e.g., Suárez-Ruiz et al., 2006) have established that elements whose concentration strongly follows the ash trend show a likely inorganic association, while organically-bound elements follow a completely opposite trend to the ash content. Only selenium seems to be mainly associated with the organic matter in sampled coals. The contents of a group of 22 minor, trace and rare earth elements (Table 6), show a weak correlation suggesting a mixed inorganic-organic association in the coal seams under consideration (Dai et al., 2021). The rest of the analyzed elements (Table 6) increases in samples parallel with ash content, which indicates a dominant affiliation with the mineral matter. No or weak correlation of several elements with ash yield may be explained by adsorption on coal surface, various modes of occurrence or anomalous low concentrations (Martínez et al., 2001). Further, positive correlations

of heavy (HREE, from Gd to Lu and Y) and light (LREE, from La to Eu) rare earth elements with Al, Ca, Fe, and P may reveal a terrigenous detrital origin for the REY species (Mishra et al., 2019). Lastly, the weak correlations ($-0.13 < r < +0.26$) between total sulfur and other elements analyzed, and no relationship between total sulfur and ash yield, reflect the mainly organic affiliation of sulfur in Marcelina coals (Hackley et al., 2005; Hackley and Martínez, 2007).

Table 6

Multivariate clustering based on elemental contents was carried out in order to identify the similarity of elements in the study coals and to group those into clusters. In coal geochemistry, this statistical tool has been usually applied in different fields such as the development of neural models to estimate moisture and ash content in coals and coaly shales (Ghosh et al., 2016) or the mode of occurrence of the trace elements in coals (Xu et al., 2021). However, it is necessary to ensure the compositional homogeneity in the dataset (Eskenezy et al., 2010). Cluster analysis was performed following the Ward's method (Everitt, 1993), and similarity percent was obtained after calculating square Euclidean distances (cut-off of 900; Fig. 4). Three groups of elements were determined. The first is wide and includes at least 12 elements within this association. Detailed analysis of these elements suggests three subgroups having a geochemical significance: Na–B and Mn–Ba–Sr, respectively, may be associated with groundwater movement and carbonate minerals (Beaton et al., 1991); while the third is made up of P, V, Zr, Li, Cu, Ni, and Cr, and these seem to be related to primary paleoproductivity and particular paleoredox conditions (Rimmer, 2004). The second group (Fe, Al, Cs, Ca, and Mg, among others) reveals a predominant clay mineral affiliation (Cullers, 1994) and, to a lesser extent, both carbonate and other possible associations. The last group includes some redox-sensitive trace elements (Mo, Rb, Nb, Co, U, Th, As, Be, and Sb; Cullers, 2002), along with another subgroup of elements (Zn, Pb, Ga, Ge, La, S, Sc, and REY) bound in sulfides, sand-forming minerals, and heavy detrital species (Ward, 2016).

Figure 4

4.2.3. Sediment source of elements

In an attempt to identify the source of trace elements in the coals under study, and considering the positive Pearson correlations between Al (Fralick and Kronberg, 1997) and trace elements such as Cr, Co, Th, Sc, La and REEs, which confirms the relative immobility of these lithophile elements (Yan et al., 2006), we can use here these latter elements to investigate the detrital input during peat accumulation in the Guasare Coalfield. In detail, the concentrations of La and Th (enriched in felsic sources) as well as Co and Sc (suggestive of mafic) may allow distinguishing between mafic and felsic provenance (e.g., Cullers, 2002). As shown in Table 7, when comparing La/Sc, Th/Sc, La/Co, and Th/Cr values of Marcelina coals with the ratios of sediments sourced from mafic and felsic rocks (Cullers et al., 1988; Cullers, 2000; Cullers and Podkovyrov, 2000), most samples lay within or closer to the felsic ranges, suggesting a probable granitic or metamorphic felsic nature of the source rocks. The La-Sc-Th ternary diagram can also give information about the provenance characteristics (Cullers, 2002). In this diagram, the average compositions of andesite and basalt (Condie, 1993), as well as some nearby granitoids (El Carmen Granodiorite and El Palmar Granite boulders; Van Der Lelij, 2013), are used for comparison purposes. The majority of samples plot near granitoid compositions (Fig. 5), which indicates that mineral fractions in Marcelina coals were derived presumably by the influence of felsic contribution.

Table 7

Figure 5

The REE distribution pattern in the sedimentary rocks is a very useful tool to unravel the provenance (Taylor and McLennan, 1985). In this regard, to identify a possible igneous source rock, the REE data of Marcelina coals are normalized relative to the chondrite values (Boynnton, 1984) and compared with granitic rocks from areas located close to the mines under study. The subscript “*n*” indicates C1- or chondrite-normalized abundances. Typical REE patterns of the Paso Diablo and Mina Norte coal samples are shown in Figure 6. They are significantly similar to each

other and those of the El Palmar Granite and El Carmen Granodiorite boulders in the foothills of the Sierra of Perijá (Van Der Lelij, 2013). The chondrite-normalized patterns of samples from both mines are characterized by a quite flat HREE shape, LREE being nearly three times higher than HREE on average and $Eu_n/Eu^* < 1$ (see Fig. 6 and Appendix A), which agree with felsic sources (e.g., granites, gneisses, and pegmatites) with clear negative Eu anomaly (Armstrong-Altrin et al., 2004), rather than Eu mobility favored by reducing and low temperature conditions during peat accumulation (Eskenazy, 1987). By contrast, granodiorite often shows a positive Eu anomaly (Cullers, 1994). Slightly negative Ce anomalies also support a felsic provenance, although other alternatives to account for a negative Ce anomaly (Ce immobility, in-situ precipitation, and Ce^{+3} to Ce^{+4} oxidation) cannot be fully ruled out (Dai et al., 2016b). Finally, coal samples show Gd_n/Yb_n and Eu_n/Eu^* ratios below 2 and not exceeding 0.85, respectively (Appendix A), which is consistent with K-feldspar-rich granitic source rocks of Cambrian age or younger (McLennan, 1989; Taylor and McLennan, 1985).

Figure 6

4.3. Mineralogy

The mineralogy of the study coal seams is quite uniform (Table 8). Quartz and kaolinite are the predominant mineral species in the low temperature ash of the samples. Although these primary minerals are usually detrital in nature (Karayiğit et al., 2018), their occurrence in the coal samples could also result from authigenic precipitation in the raised peat mires protected from clastic inflow at the time of peatification (Ward, 2016). This would be consistent with a progradational deltaic environment for the Marcelina coals (Hackley and Martínez, 2007). A series of secondary minerals identified in the coal samples include illite, K-feldspar, sphalerite, pyrite, plagioclase, diaspore, hematite, and apatite, among others; which are also present in small proportions (see Table 8).

Table 8

Traces of bassanite were also detected in the LTA residues. Although Ca sulfates may represent either authigenic sediments or crystallization of ions from aqueous solution in the coal pore structure with evaporation, they were probably formed during the LTA process (Koukouzas et al., 2010). Butlerite and whewellite are rare minerals in coals and they are, respectively, a product of oxidation of pyrite (Kruszewski, 2013) and the result of an authigenic accumulation of Ca oxalate in coal seams (Echigo and Kimata, 2010). Carbonate minerals consist of small quantities of ankerite and siderite, which are the dominant iron-bearing species in coals when pyrite is absent or found in very low amounts (Ward et al., 2001), and they both would have been authigenically precipitated within mires in early diagenetic stages into the Paleocene (Ward et al. 1996), which is agreement with the freshwater conditions in which the study coals were formed (Hackley and Martínez, 2007). Oriented-aggregate XRD analysis indicated that kaolinite is the dominant component of the clay fraction of the study coals, and that illite and other clay minerals are usually present in minor and trace amounts, respectively. The predominance of kaolinite over the other minerals in the clay fraction, along with presence of whewellite and bassanite in the LTA materials, agree with a low detrital input to the paleomire and a significant portion of Ca associated to organic macerals (Koukouzas et al., 2010). Differences in illite contents in our samples can reveal subtle changes in provenance and depositional setting (Escobar et al., 2016).

4.4. Coalbed methane in the Marcelina seams

4.4.1. Numerical modeling of gas generated by Guasare coals

Generation of methane during coalification is modeled by calculating the amounts of volatiles in view of the atomic H/C and O/C ratios at the beginning of the high-volatile bituminous rank (0.85 and 0.13; Kopp et al., 2000) and averages of both ratios for Guasare coals (0.78 and 0.066). More exactly, complex organic “molecules” break down, releasing volatiles, and are gradually converted to hard coal and finally graphite, with decreasing atomic H/C and O/C ratios down to near zero

(Suggate, 2002). Only methane, carbon dioxide and water molecules were considered in order to simplify the modeling process. Other assumptions of the model are: methane is not significantly generated during early stages of coalification (Kopp et al., 2000) and the fact that the ratio of carbon dioxide to methane as gases released from organic matter is assumed to be 2 at maturity levels (~0.75%) of high-volatile bituminous A Guasare coals (Kopp et al., 2000; Escobar et al., 2016).

Once the numerical analysis described by Kopp and Bennett (2001) was carried out (Appendix B), we also assumed a mass loss of around 33% during the transition from lignite to high-volatile bituminous A coal (Tang et al., 1996). The model has predicted a methane generative potential of ~11 cm³ per gram of raw coal and CBM reserves in the Guasare Coalfield near 17.6 billion m³.

4.4.2. Methane sorption capacity of Guasare coals

Table 2 shows the values for gas volume per unit weight of each sampled coal seam (G_c). High pressure desorption data from dried coal samples indicated methane sorption capacity data ranging from 5.87 to 13.0 cm³/g, approaching the economic threshold of 9.30 cm³/g (Tang et al., 1996). These results were slightly lower than the dry, ash-free coalbed gas contents (G_{daf}) estimated theoretically by an indirect method from seam depth and proximate data (1.60-16.4 cm³/g; Juliao, 2010), which reveals that Guasare coals could accommodate more gas than it would be present in them. Experimental data are also coherent with methane storage capacities (3.42-13.0 cm³/g) of raw Guasare coals reported by Tyler et al. (2006), thereby suggesting that Marcelina seams can be considered to contain notable amounts of coal-bed methane.

The gas content values (G_c) for the Guasare Coalfield represents only the total volume of gas that is adsorbed by van der Waals forces to coal's interior surface area, but not to gas retention in other forms such as free gas present in the open pore spaces of coal and within natural cleats and

fractures, dissolved in formation water, and trapped gas within the matrix porosity (Clarkson and Bustin, 1996). Our results tend to underestimate the methane sorption capacity of Guasare coals due to gas loss after sampling and during crushing of samples. Hence, according to Strapóć et al. (2007), the measured gas content is equivalent to the residual gas fraction and to a part of the desorbed gas.

4.4.3. Clay content and CBM accumulation

Among the few studies have been carried out on the role of clays in methane sorption capacity of coal, Lu et al. (1995) indicated that illite is able to sorb methane at pressures from 1 to 7 MPa. Knowing that moisture in coal reduces the ability of the clay fraction to retain methane because moisture occupies sorption sites within the clays (Chalmers et al., 2008), total clay and illite contents are plotted versus the gas content on 16 dried samples (Fig. 7) in order to evaluate possible secondary influences of both variables on methane sorption capacity. Normalized data are presented on a per unit TOC volume basis assuming that the density of kerogen remains constant.

Figure 7

Negligible trend exists between gas content normalized to TOC and total clay content (Fig. 7a), in contrast to the positive relationship between methane sorption capacity normalized to TOC and illite content considering a sufficiently broad range (0.5-5%) of the latter variable (Fig. 7b), reflecting the notion that kaolinite and quartz have low sorption capacity compared to illite and the positive relationship of the latter clay with the surface area (Chalmers et al., 2008).

5. Conclusions

The high volatile bituminous A coals of the Guasare Coalfield contain low proportions of mineral matter and show no regular vertical and lateral variation in mineralogy and inorganic geochemistry. Kaolinite and quartz are the dominant mineral phases in selected Marcelina coal seams. In general, mean values of trace element concentrations in Marcelina coals generally indicate strong depletion

compared to the averages for world hard coals. Although this latter geochemical characteristic can make difficult a reliable statistical analysis to elucidate the modes of occurrence of elements, they all (except Se) show inorganic affinity or intermediate association and mixed mode of occurrence.

Regarding the provenance of trace and rare earth elements in Marcelina coals, Th/Sc, Th/Co, Th/Cr, La/Sc, LREE enrichment, and clear negative Eu anomalies reveal the predominant felsic character of the source rocks. Similarly, La-Th-Sc values and low Eu_n/Eu^* ratios are in agreement with Phanerozoic granitoids and their metamorphic equivalents as source rocks. Lastly, although a sediment contribution from metamorphic rocks of the Perijá Formation and other possibilities (as la Luna carbonate rocks and relatively nearby La Quinta mafic volcanoclastic materials; see Haze, 1984) cannot be completely dismissed, the comparison of REE patterns and Eu anomalies to the source rocks suggests that the mineral matter in Marcelina coals was, in part, a result of detrital input derived from granitoids such as the El Palmar Granite and El Carmen Granodiorite boulders or other similar granitic rocks. Data from raw Guasare coals indicates that methane contents range from 5 to 11 cm^3/g , values similar to that obtained from the numerical model (near 11 cm^3/g). Finally, the illite content showed a positive relationship with gas storage capacity when this latter is normalized to TOC on dried coal samples.

CRedit author statement

Gonzalo Márquez: Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft, Investigation, Supervision;

Manuel Martínez: Writing - Review & Editing, Formal analysis, Validation; **Gabriela Carruyo:**

Visualization, Investigation; **Carlos Boente:** Writing - Review & Editing, Formal analysis; **Erika**

Lorenzo: Investigation, Data curation; **Rafael Tocco:** Writing - Review & Editing, Resources.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. There are no conflicts of interest to declare.

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Figure 1: a) and b), respectively, maps showing the location of the Guasare Coalfield in NW Venezuela and the Paso Diablo and open-pit mines in this basin (modified from Escobar et al., 2016); c) situation of exploratory boreholes.

Figure 2: Stratigraphic units in the Sierra of Perijá (modified from Escobar et al., 2016).

Figure 3: Lithologic column of the Paso Diablo and Mina Norte open-cut mines showing coal seam names and stratigraphic position of coal samples (modified from Quintero et al., 2011).

Figure 4: Dendrogram showing correlation of elements in the Marcelina coal seams.

Figure 5: La-Sc-Th triangular diagram for the coals under study. Data from local granitoids (El Palmar Granite and El Carmen Granodiorite; Van Der Lelij, 2013) are included.

Figure 6: Chondrite-normalized REE plots for the Guasare coals, El Palmar and El Carmen granitoids.

Figure 7: Plots of gas content normalized to per-unit TOC on a dried basis with the total clay (a) and illite (b) contents.

Age		Unit	Lithology	
Pleistocene		El Milagro	Coarse-grained sandstone and conglomerates	80 m
Pliocene		La Villa	Sandstone alternating with carbonaceous shales	1130 m 2630 m
Miocene	Upper	Los Ranchos	Coarse-grained sandstone alternating with gray shales	
	Middle	Cuiba	Shales, sandstones and siltstones	
	Lower	Macoa	Carbonaceous shales, sandstones and siltstones	
Oligocene		Peroc	Siltstones and sandstone	4400 m 4540 m 5840 m
		Ceibote	Massive sandstones	
Eocene		La Sierra	Sandstone and shales	
		Misoa	Sandstone and shales	
Paleocene		Marcelina	Limestones, sandstone, shales and coal.	6370 m
		Guasare	Limestones and sandstone	6760 m
Cretaceous	Upper	Mito Juan	Siltstones	7660 m 7860 m
		Colón	Gray shales	
		La Luna	Organic matter-rich and black limestones and shales	
	Lower	Cogollo Group	Biomicritic limestones, shales and sandstones	8510 m 10110 m
		Rio Negro	Coarse-grained, arkosic and fine-grained sandstones	
Jurassic	Upper	La Quinta	Siltstone, sandstones and red conglomerates	14110 m
	Middle	Macoíta	Calcareous siltstones interbedded with tuffs and argillaceous material	
	Lower	Tinacoa	Limestones and sandstones with piroclastic material	
Triassic		El Totumo	Trachytes, dacites, tuffs and porphyritic latites	14610 m 14860 m
Permian		Palmarito	Calcareous Shales, marls and limestones	
Carboniferous	Upper	Río Palmar	Limestones, marls and calcareous mudstones	15060 m
		Caño Indio	Sandstones alternating with shales and red siltstones	17560 m
	Lower	Chachirí Group	Black and grey shales, sandstones and Limestones	
Devonian				

Figure 5

Table 1: Coordinates of exploratory wells and list of coal seams under study. Codes in boldface represent the sampled coal seams.

Pit area	Well	Latitude	Longitude	Studied coal seams
Aceitunos	1	11°03'34"N	72°16'22"W	4MO/5O
	2	11°03'46"N	72°15'44"W	2J/2M/3K/3M/4MO
	3	11°03'47"N	72°15'36"W	2I/2J/2M/2O/3G/3H/3K/3M/4MO
	4	11°03'14"N	72°15'58"W	4MO/5M/5O/6K/6M/6O/6Q/7M/7O/8KM
	5	11°03'15"N	72°15'59"W	4MO/5M/5O/6MO/6Q/7M/7O/8I/8KM/9O
Baqueta	6	11°01'45"N	72°16'40"W	4M/4O/5M
	7	11°01'44"N	72°17'03"W	4M/5M/6K/6MO/6Q/7M/7O
	8	11°01'58"N	72°16'43"W	3G/3H/3K/4O
	9	11°01'57"N	72°16'21"W	4M/4O/5O/6K/6MO/6Q/7M/7O/8K/8M
Paso Diablo	10	11°00'41"N	72°16'42"W	3G/4MO/5M/5O/5Q/6K/6MO/6Q
	11	11°00'37"N	72°17'20"W	2I/2K/2M1/2M2/2N/3H/3I/3K/3M/3N
	12	11°00'06"N	72°16'42"W	3G/4MO/5M/5O/6MO/6Q/7M/7O/8I/8K/8M/9G/9J/9K/9M/9O/10M/10N/11M
	13	10°59'49"N	72°17'04"W	4MO/5M/5O/5Q/6K/6MO/7M/7O/8I/8K
Mina Norte	14	11°05'35"N	71°14'55"W	4M
	15	11°04'39"N	72°15'05"W	2I/3K
	16	11°04'30"N	72°15'01"W	2K/3I

Table 2: Depths (m), thicknesses (m), TOC (wt.%), proximate-ultimate parameters and gross calorific values (MJ/Kg on a moist ash-free basis), G_{daf} and G_c (cm³/g) for Marcelina coal seams studied. The codes for coal seam numbering precede those for exploratory wells in sampling nomenclature.

Coal	Depth	Thickness	Moisture	Ash yield	VM	FC	C	H	N	O	S _t	TOC	GCV	H/C	O/C	G_{daf}	G_c
5O/1	37.8	1.9	1.7	9.9	42.3	50.8	82.54	5.44	1.87	7.42	0.57	73.07	34.48	0.79	0.067	7.14	6.31
4MO/1	78.7	14.5	1.9	1.9	39.2	59.6	84.24	5.42	1.91	7.58	0.44	--	34.99	0.77	0.068	10.4	--
4MO/2	34.7	14.8	2.4	1.7	39.9	59.0	87.47	4.93	1.68	7.87	0.45	--	35.32	0.67	0.066	7.78	--
3K/2	125.4	2.3	2.1	3.9	43.5	54.3	82.61	5.77	1.67	7.43	0.57	78.32	33.69	0.83	0.068	11.5	9.17
3M/2	131.6	1.8	1.6	2.8	43.3	55.4	81.06	5.59	1.84	7.29	0.69	--	34.23	0.82	0.067	11.9	--
2J/2	150.7	0.7	3.3	4.5	44.3	52.2	83.85	5.73	1.90	6.94	0.65	--	35.41	0.82	0.062	11.9	--
2M/2	159.8	2.6	2.9	1.4	43.6	55.6	84.52	5.74	1.72	7.24	0.83	79.43	34.29	0.81	0.064	12.7	11.1
4MO/3	48.0	14.6	2.1	2.1	39.7	59.0	85.02	5.30	1.83	7.65	0.51	79.21	35.07	0.74	0.067	8.72	7.19
3G/3	89.4	0.5	2.3	2.5	43.2	55.4	80.85	5.84	1.73	7.07	0.84	--	34.54	0.86	0.065	10.4	--
3H/3	99.4	1.0	0.9	2.6	45.5	53.0	81.82	5.74	1.85	7.36	1.00	--	34.72	0.84	0.067	10.8	--
3K/3	139.3	2.4	2.5	4.6	45.2	51.3	82.03	5.65	1.86	6.86	0.47	--	34.61	0.82	0.062	11.6	--
3M/3	144.5	2.1	3.3	1.6	45.1	53.9	82.82	5.80	1.88	7.45	0.73	--	35.11	0.84	0.066	12.1	--
2I/3	158.1	0.8	1.8	2.0	44.2	54.6	82.59	5.82	1.87	7.13	0.63	--	33.85	0.84	0.064	12.6	--
2J/3	162.5	0.5	3.8	4.4	42.6	51.9	84.04	5.72	1.71	7.56	0.79	--	35.46	0.81	0.068	12.1	--
2M/3	177.3	3.3	2.9	1.9	45.2	53.7	82.79	5.85	1.98	7.45	0.60	--	35.16	0.84	0.067	12.9	--
2O/3	198.2	1.5	1.9	1.8	44.6	54.4	82.09	5.78	1.66	7.38	0.38	73.20	34.81	0.84	0.067	13.6	12.3
8KM/4	0.9	3.0	1.3	1.6	41.5	57.5	81.32	5.03	1.84	7.31	0.72	--	33.51	0.74	0.067	1.60	--
7M/4	11.1	4.0	2.1	1.5	39.3	59.8	86.04	5.16	1.75	7.74	1.06	--	35.25	0.71	0.068	5.18	--
7O/4	23.2	3.8	1.7	0.9	41.6	57.6	81.86	5.21	1.76	7.36	0.59	80.04	33.93	0.76	0.065	6.76	5.92
6K/4	38.4	0.5	1.0	4.5	37.0	60.1	84.10	5.36	1.91	8.20	1.25	--	33.65	0.76	0.073	8.09	--
6M/4	49.1	3.1	2.1	1.3	40.6	58.6	86.87	5.05	1.87	7.81	1.56	73.22	35.33	0.69	0.067	8.81	7.14
6O/4	52.7	2.9	1.9	1.9	40.3	58.2	86.32	5.29	1.96	7.76	0.56	74.06	35.48	0.73	0.065	8.98	7.28
6Q/4	65.4	0.7	1.8	5.0	42.1	58.5	81.79	5.46	1.85	7.35	1.32	77.85	34.32	0.79	0.063	9.32	7.75
5M/4	78.6	3.9	1.8	1.5	40.4	58.7	84.00	5.52	1.70	8.56	0.80	--	35.09	0.78	0.070	10.4	--
5O/4	107.3	2.8	2.0	2.5	40.0	58.4	83.99	5.58	1.80	8.15	0.84	79.26	35.18	0.79	0.072	11.3	9.36
4MO/4	148.9	13.2	1.6	1.3	38.4	60.7	86.64	5.12	1.76	6.79	0.69	80.59	35.35	0.71	0.060	13.0	10.4
9O/5	37.7	1.9	2.2	2.8	42.8	55.6	81.69	5.40	1.85	8.35	0.57	--	34.22	0.79	0.076	7.76	--
8I/5	47.8	1.9	2.3	3.5	42.4	55.5	84.98	5.62	1.93	7.28	0.64	--	34.25	0.79	0.064	8.37	--
8KM/5	53.6	2.7	1.9	1.4	39.3	59.8	83.99	5.67	1.70	7.19	1.01	--	34.10	0.80	0.066	9.17	--
7M/5	62.2	3.9	2.6	1.3	41.2	56.8	84.87	5.47	1.92	7.27	0.81	--	34.01	0.77	0.064	9.42	--
7O/5	74.9	3.6	1.9	1.1	41.4	57.9	82.46	5.14	1.77	7.42	0.67	80.31	34.03	0.74	0.067	10.2	8.18
6MO/5	102.0	6.2	2.1	2.0	40.5	58.2	83.43	5.06	1.89	8.05	0.89	79.57	34.25	0.72	0.072	11.2	8.93

Sample	Depth	Thickness	Moisture	Ash yield	VM	FC	C	H	N	O	St	TOC	GCV	H/C	O/C	G _{daf}	G _c
6Q/5	117.7	0.9	1.7	4.2	42.9	55.4	82.27	5.48	1.86	7.40	1.04	76.80	34.45	0.79	0.067	11.3	8.94
5M/5	132.6	4.2	1.7	1.7	40.6	58.3	85.93	5.71	1.75	7.28	0.75	--	34.37	0.79	0.063	12.3	--
5O/5	160.0	2.8	2.1	1.3	39.6	59.5	84.72	5.22	1.92	7.62	0.89	78.17	35.01	0.73	0.065	13.1	10.4
4MO/5	201.2	13.5	1.9	1.4	38.4	60.7	84.35	5.42	1.91	7.59	0.33	78.26	35.01	0.77	0.066	14.2	11.3
5M/6	77.1	5.8	1.5	0.9	40.3	59.1	84.16	5.36	1.91	8.37	0.98	77.51	34.93	0.76	0.071	10.4	8.62
4M/6	102.3	2.5	2.2	1.6	41.9	57.1	83.74	5.28	1.90	6.92	0.79	78.01	34.66	0.75	0.061	11.1	8.89
4O/6	138.0	8.8	1.9	1.1	42.5	56.5	81.75	5.46	1.85	7.35	0.63	79.84	34.30	0.79	0.067	12.3	9.80
7M/7	97.4	1.9	2.5	1.5	42.9	56.5	84.20	5.67	1.91	7.57	0.82	--	35.37	0.80	0.067	10.9	--
7O/7	107.4	3.9	1.0	2.8	41.9	56.4	82.38	5.24	1.77	7.17	0.75	80.88	34.16	0.76	0.065	11.3	9.03
6K/7	128.1	1.0	2.3	4.9	43.1	53.1	85.49	5.30	1.94	8.24	1.05	--	33.85	0.74	0.070	11.4	--
6MO/7	137.1	5.5	1.7	3.8	42.1	55.6	84.07	5.50	1.71	7.56	0.78	77.93	35.08	0.78	0.068	12.0	9.53
6Q/7	152.8	1.0	2.1	5.3	43.4	53.3	85.75	5.73	1.64	7.26	0.77	--	34.38	0.79	0.064	12.0	--
5M/7	163.6	3.8	1.8	2.9	43.1	55.3	81.75	5.46	1.85	7.35	0.96	--	34.29	0.80	0.069	12.7	--
4M/7	222.3	9.9	1.8	1.0	42.7	56.7	83.47	5.54	1.89	7.01	0.51	78.67	35.06	0.79	0.063	14.3	11.5
4O/8	27.4	2.8	1.3	3.0	42.0	56.3	84.21	5.53	1.91	7.57	0.82	--	35.17	0.78	0.066	7.01	--
3G/8	51.5	0.6	2.8	4.8	44.2	53.9	82.39	5.66	1.87	7.41	0.74	--	34.77	0.82	0.069	8.33	--
3H/8	61.3	0.8	1.6	4.5	44.9	52.5	82.65	5.81	1.74	7.43	0.97	--	35.09	0.84	0.065	8.94	--
3K/8	96.1	1.1	2.0	3.5	44.0	54.0	79.66	5.73	1.81	7.16	0.94	76.64	34.01	0.86	0.065	10.5	8.93
8K/9	93.0	3.9	2.7	4.4	42.1	52.9	85.22	5.17	1.93	7.66	0.99	--	34.99	0.72	0.065	10.3	--
8M/9	100.1	0.9	2.4	4.5	38.8	57.3	81.43	5.41	1.84	7.31	0.78	--	34.21	0.79	0.068	10.8	--
7M/9	115.4	3.1	2.7	1.5	41.4	57.7	82.18	5.14	1.86	7.39	0.68	--	33.94	0.75	0.066	11.6	--
7O/9	129.4	3.7	2.6	3.7	43.0	54.0	81.41	5.40	1.84	6.92	0.96	76.77	34.13	0.79	0.065	11.6	9.14
6K/9	149.4	0.8	1.7	3.1	42.9	58.1	84.59	5.61	1.92	7.24	1.09	--	34.35	0.79	0.064	12.4	--
6MO/9	159.1	6.8	2.9	1.7	40.5	58.4	82.99	5.22	1.68	7.46	0.99	79.18	34.37	0.75	0.063	12.8	10.3
6Q/9	174.4	0.9	2.2	5.8	42.9	52.1	83.35	5.38	1.79	8.23	1.51	--	34.66	0.77	0.070	12.4	--
5O/9	216.0	2.5	2.1	1.7	41.7	57.3	82.95	5.40	1.88	7.46	0.81	79.84	34.58	0.78	0.069	14.1	11.2
4M/9	254.7	8.8	2.6	1.1	39.7	59.7	85.78	4.97	1.94	7.72	0.56	77.92	34.85	0.69	0.066	15.1	11.9
4O/9	272.3	6.6	3.1	5.6	44.7	54.4	84.11	5.35	1.91	7.56	0.49	81.99	34.85	0.76	0.067	13.0	8.95
6K/10	14.9	1.6	1.2	4.9	36.6	59.5	85.32	5.26	1.63	6.82	0.93	--	33.55	0.73	0.060	5.73	--
6MO/10	25.4	4.6	2.0	1.5	41.0	58.2	84.66	5.48	1.92	7.25	0.62	79.09	33.94	0.77	0.064	6.96	5.87
6Q/10	43.6	0.9	1.3	4.9	42.7	52.3	85.93	5.27	1.95	7.28	1.03	--	33.72	0.73	0.063	7.98	--
5M/10	64.7	5.5	1.7	2.4	41.2	57.3	82.82	4.98	1.88	7.45	0.94	--	33.94	0.72	0.067	9.54	--
5O/10	91.2	2.8	1.9	1.3	40.7	58.6	81.86	5.42	1.76	7.36	0.56	80.24	34.23	0.79	0.068	10.9	8.88
5Q/10	129.7	1.2	1.8	5.4	39.5	55.4	82.27	5.10	1.66	7.40	0.92	--	33.94	0.74	0.067	11.6	--

Sample	Depth	Thickness	Moisture	Ash yield	VM	FC	C	H	N	O	St	TOC	GCV	H/C	O/C	G _{daf}	G _c
4MO/10	223.2	9.6	1.6	4.3	41.6	57.3	81.84	5.48	1.85	7.36	0.66	80.38	34.34	0.79	0.068	14.0	11.0
3G/10	254.3	0.5	2.4	3.2	43.4	54.8	81.54	5.71	1.68	8.33	0.84	--	33.93	0.84	0.071	14.4	--
3H/11	60.1	1.0	1.3	4.6	43.7	53.3	82.95	5.71	1.88	6.86	0.85	--	35.03	0.82	0.062	8.96	--
3I/11	70.8	0.6	1.2	3.7	45.6	51.1	80.46	5.74	1.82	8.21	0.87	--	34.29	0.85	0.070	9.45	--
3K/11	96.3	1.6	2.4	3.3	43.4	54.8	81.58	5.87	1.85	8.34	0.92	76.26	34.18	0.86	0.076	10.6	8.45
3M/11	100.6	0.6	1.2	7.3	43.1	52.7	84.13	5.80	1.72	7.57	0.81	--	33.60	0.82	0.068	10.4	--
3N/11	106.3	0.9	1.2	1.4	43.4	55.8	81.47	5.88	1.85	7.33	0.49	--	34.12	0.86	0.063	11.3	--
2I/11	116.8	1.0	2.7	3.0	48.1	50.3	84.65	5.82	1.92	7.25	0.58	--	34.42	0.82	0.064	11.0	--
2K/11	123.6	0.5	1.1	5.2	44.9	52.2	82.65	5.81	1.87	7.43	0.85	--	35.08	0.84	0.066	11.3	--
2M1/11	128.4	1.1	2.9	1.8	43.4	55.6	83.26	5.66	1.79	7.19	0.93	77.09	35.25	0.81	0.064	11.8	9.39
2M2/11	130.0	1.4	1.5	3.2	43.3	54.8	82.82	5.75	1.78	7.45	0.69	76.90	33.74	0.83	0.065	11.8	9.42
2N/11	147.3	1.0	2.6	2.7	45.9	51.6	82.86	5.85	1.88	8.45	0.96	--	35.21	0.84	0.071	12.0	--
11M/12	11.2	0.5	2.7	3.7	38.6	58.3	80.32	5.18	1.82	7.22	0.68	--	33.40	0.77	0.063	5.04	--
10M/12	38.0	2.8	0.9	5.0	40.0	57.0	81.30	5.03	1.84	7.31	0.54	--	33.49	0.74	0.069	7.84	--
10N/12	45.8	1.9	1.1	4.7	39.4	57.8	85.63	5.68	1.56	6.56	0.56	--	33.63	0.79	0.058	8.41	--
9G/12	105.2	5.3	3.1	2.0	42.0	55.9	80.52	5.22	1.83	6.95	0.59	--	33.51	0.77	0.064	11.0	--
9J/12	126.6	0.9	1.6	2.8	39.9	58.4	80.58	5.36	1.83	7.24	0.75	--	33.79	0.79	0.068	12.0	--
9K/12	128.1	1.5	0.9	1.0	39.8	59.5	81.68	5.45	1.85	7.34	0.33	--	33.66	0.79	0.063	12.3	--
9M/12	140.6	0.5	3.2	5.9	37.0	56.8	86.11	5.27	1.95	7.74	0.62	--	35.39	0.73	0.067	11.9	--
9O/12	144.8	0.7	1.1	4.0	39.6	57.9	85.47	5.53	1.94	8.24	0.46	--	33.94	0.77	0.072	12.4	--
8I/12	184.5	1.2	1.0	4.3	40.7	56.8	84.52	5.64	1.62	7.60	0.67	--	35.53	0.79	0.065	13.3	--
8K/12	191.6	1.6	1.6	7.2	41.7	52.9	82.69	4.99	1.87	7.44	0.64	--	33.89	0.72	0.067	12.8	--
8M/12	194.4	1.1	1.2	5.1	41.4	55.5	81.32	5.11	1.74	7.31	0.83	--	33.64	0.75	0.068	13.3	--
7M/12	210.9	3.0	1.2	1.6	39.1	59.9	83.10	5.07	1.88	7.47	0.49	--	34.12	0.73	0.066	14.4	--
7O/12	225.8	3.4	2.5	0.9	41.7	57.7	84.95	5.70	1.93	7.28	0.48	--	34.34	0.80	0.064	14.4	--
6MO/12	255.2	6.7	1.4	3.2	42.6	56.5	83.09	5.27	1.88	6.97	0.47	81.09	34.40	0.76	0.062	14.7	11.2
6Q/12	271.3	1.4	3.0	4.6	42.3	53.6	82.56	5.38	1.87	7.43	1.55	--	34.41	0.78	0.066	14.4	--
5M/12	289.3	5.9	1.4	2.7	40.8	57.6	83.07	5.51	1.88	7.47	0.90	--	34.82	0.79	0.065	15.5	--
5O/12	308.8	2.5	1.6	0.7	38.0	61.6	85.04	5.65	1.56	7.11	0.64	79.99	34.51	0.79	0.063	16.4	13.0
4MO/12	345.6	11.0	1.7	1.3	42.3	56.9	83.75	5.56	1.90	7.53	0.47	80.51	35.03	0.79	0.068	16.4	12.8
3G/12	377.4	0.5	0.9	3.6	44.9	49.0	82.94	5.85	1.85	7.06	0.87	--	35.23	0.84	0.063	16.1	--
8I/13	61.8	1.1	1.2	0.7	38.1	61.4	85.04	5.62	1.93	7.20	0.79	--	33.96	0.79	0.062	9.86	--
8K/13	70.0	1.4	3.1	5.1	37.3	58.2	81.61	5.43	1.84	8.33	0.54	--	33.82	0.79	0.072	9.57	--
7M/13	90.8	2.8	2.6	1.2	42.7	56.5	85.48	5.65	1.94	8.32	0.52	--	33.91	0.79	0.071	10.7	--

Sample	Depth	Thickness	Moisture	Ash yield	VM	FC	C	H	N	O	St	TOC	GCV	H/C	O/C	G_{daf}	G_c
7O/13	105.3	3.1	2.2	1.1	42.8	56.5	83.72	4.97	1.99	7.54	0.59	79.16	34.18	0.71	0.062	11.2	8.92
6K/13	131.6	1.6	0.9	4.5	41.9	52.0	82.50	5.13	1.86	7.48	0.91	--	34.07	0.74	0.068	11.7	--
6MO/13	135.0	4.8	2.2	1.7	43.2	55.8	83.83	5.08	1.73	7.14	0.61	78.76	34.38	0.72	0.063	12.1	9.34
5M/13	168.1	5.2	1.9	2.5	42.3	56.3	82.50	5.50	1.67	7.41	0.48	--	34.66	0.79	0.066	12.9	--
5O/13	184.0	2.2	2.0	3.0	41.2	57.0	83.54	5.20	1.89	7.51	0.50	79.55	34.45	0.74	0.067	13.3	10.3
5Q/13	209.8	0.7	1.2	2.5	41.0	57.5	82.60	5.39	1.87	7.43	0.70	--	34.44	0.78	0.066	14.1	--
4MO/13	228.7	9.2	1.4	1.4	41.4	57.8	83.26	5.50	1.69	7.08	0.40	--	34.85	0.79	0.064	14.6	--
4M/14	147.4	1.6	2.8	1.8	38.1	59.9	82.39	5.52	1.50	8.27	0.42	79.11	34.11	0.79	0.075	12.7	10.2
2I/15	171.2	1.0	1.4	5.4	43.5	53.3	83.48	5.74	1.69	7.51	0.69	80.89	33.30	0.82	0.067	12.5	11.0
3K/15	105.4	0.8	1.9	3.2	47.0	51.0	85.00	5.84	1.59	6.87	0.70	78.76	34.70	0.82	0.061	10.7	8.69
2K/16	181.6	1.9	3.4	5.0	44.9	49.0	81.71	5.73	1.85	7.35	0.49	75.00	34.63	0.84	0.067	10.1	8.69
3I/16	97.7	1.4	2.5	2.5	43.7	54.9	85.22	5.93	1.44	6.60	0.81	74.11	33.77	0.86	0.059	13.1	12.0

Notes: Proximate-ultimate data in wt. % on a dry basis, except VM (wt. % on a dry ash-free basis), H/C and O/C (atomic ratios); depth, moisture and ash yield are expressed by "h", "m" and "a"; $G_{daf} = 0.01 \cdot (100 - m - a) \cdot [(0.8 \cdot FC / VM + 5.6) \cdot (0.096 \cdot h)^{0.315} \cdot (0.096 \cdot h)^{0.01 \cdot VM / FC} - 0.14 \cdot (0.018 \cdot h + 11)]$ (Kim, 1977).

Table 3: Contents, means and concentration coefficients (CC) of minor and trace elements determined by ICP-AES in Marcelina coal samples ($\mu\text{g/g}$ unless indicated %).

Sample	Al,%	Fe,%	P	Mg	Mn	Ca	Na	K	Ti	Zn	B	Sr	Ba	Cr	V	Ni	Pb
5O/1	0.44	0.40	126.0	202.1	17.6	508.8	432.8	297.8	177.9	6.6	36.2	16.9	30.5	6.0	8.4	8.3	2.6
3K/2	0.26	0.13	8.1	42.3	5.0	64.1	133.0	9.4	24.6	2.5	26.3	9.8	6.5	1.1	1.7	1.1	1.9
2M/2	0.14	0.03	8.0	2.6	0.9	22.8	101.5	16.7	23.1	2.5	30.6	5.4	10.2	1.4	5.0	2.1	2.3
4MO/3	0.15	0.07	15.6	22.7	3.2	32.9	109.0	11.2	39.9	1.3	17.2	4.5	4.1	1.8	2.2	2.2	2.3
2O/3	0.06	0.07	9.2	128.6	7.4	440.3	102.8	11.0	36.9	0.6	18.1	10.6	4.3	1.4	2.2	1.0	2.5
7O/4	0.03	0.13	7.7	24.3	4.7	68.7	222.2	37.8	14.1	1.1	19.3	4.4	6.3	1.1	1.0	1.0	1.8
6M/4	0.02	0.19	23.5	88.0	6.7	156.8	129.0	14.8	29.4	0.7	25.9	14.4	14.6	2.0	2.7	0.6	0.7
6O/4	0.18	0.15	32.9	60.4	6.7	168.2	170.7	106.7	37.2	1.6	37.5	9.8	2.2	2.2	3.5	1.4	2.0
6Q/4	0.49	0.24	44.7	12.7	1.7	52.7	166.6	322.0	97.8	0.9	23.5	13.2	5.7	5.0	6.6	6.1	1.9
5O/4	0.03	0.11	8.4	2.5	0.5	32.6	53.2	293.3	181.5	1.0	20.6	5.0	4.8	1.6	5.5	4.4	1.2
4MO/4	0.14	0.07	19.2	16.4	1.7	84.9	155.3	36.5	87.0	1.0	22.6	14.1	16.3	2.1	4.1	1.9	1.8
7O/5	0.08	0.29	7.2	136.7	15.3	344.1	190.0	29.5	42.9	1.1	34.1	9.9	10.1	2.3	5.3	2.3	2.0
6MO/5	0.23	0.14	11.2	70.2	16.3	184.8	289.1	154.0	60.9	3.9	16.8	8.8	7.0	2.4	4.0	2.0	2.1
6Q/5	0.47	0.06	104.5	4.7	3.5	400.7	157.7	13.8	25.5	1.3	13.2	27.6	3.9	1.4	0.9	1.9	1.7
5O/5	0.19	0.08	24.7	12.3	2.6	24.7	270.8	12.7	61.2	5.2	41.7	5.9	6.3	5.3	8.8	5.0	1.3
4MO/5	0.10	0.08	15.2	20.2	1.9	112.5	190.0	20.8	62.4	0.5	16.2	15.3	17.1	1.5	1.2	1.5	1.2
5M/6	0.13	0.17	6.8	306.0	12.0	24.0	161.5	51.2	153.0	2.6	26.0	5.1	14.5	1.7	4.2	3.6	1.1
4M/6	0.12	0.30	12.8	286.1	19.7	472.6	126.4	22.0	53.4	0.9	16.1	17.6	5.7	1.5	2.0	1.1	1.8
4O/6	0.14	0.51	19.2	84.4	6.3	272.3	152.8	23.7	103.8	2.1	29.6	13.4	10.4	2.4	5.6	4.2	2.2
7O/7	0.19	0.30	15.2	302.8	23.5	704.7	179.4	43.8	129.6	1.7	24.8	19.6	27.5	1.9	4.6	2.5	2.1
6MO/7	0.23	0.11	13.2	84.9	4.2	276.4	227.0	129.4	165.0	1.7	33.9	28.7	11.1	3.1	7.1	6.0	1.6
4M/7	0.03	0.09	5.6	10.8	3.8	24.9	184.6	314.4	34.2	1.6	29.7	5.5	8.9	1.9	1.9	1.5	1.6
3K/8	0.25	0.30	19.3	204.3	18.6	460.2	168.1	95.6	87.9	3.3	32.3	18.0	21.6	3.1	8.5	3.6	2.6
7O/9	0.36	0.22	16.8	22.9	5.8	76.7	138.3	129.7	70.2	1.0	18.9	9.1	25.7	1.2	1.0	0.7	1.1
6MO/9	0.05	0.47	72.7	84.1	16.3	232.8	265.6	94.0	111.0	3.4	18.4	21.5	7.4	2.3	3.1	1.2	1.6
5O/9	0.04	0.25	16.0	11.8	11.6	42.4	272.4	44.9	40.8	3.7	33.1	9.2	5.4	1.9	3.9	5.5	0.5
4M/9	0.11	0.27	8.8	12.7	11.3	92.2	175.5	14.0	28.8	1.5	15.2	5.9	4.3	1.8	1.2	0.9	1.2
4O/9	0.19	0.11	14.8	4.2	1.4	16.6	216.7	34.8	29.4	1.1	18.0	4.5	10.9	1.4	1.4	2.6	0.1
6MO/10	0.02	0.18	4.9	8.6	3.5	68.9	105.4	17.0	68.4	2.5	18.1	9.0	6.5	1.6	2.0	1.6	1.6
5O/10	0.16	0.13	34.0	46.3	12.3	68.5	211.3	64.5	30.6	3.9	28.8	4.2	11.8	1.6	2.2	5.5	2.2
4MO/10	0.49	0.27	26.4	56.0	2.6	182.2	334.2	286.0	114.9	4.6	19.8	18.1	18.8	4.1	6.3	2.6	2.5

Sample	Al,%	Fe,%	P	Mg	Mn	Ca	Na	K	Ti	Zn	B	Sr	Ba	Cr	V	Ni	Pb
3K/11	0.26	0.18	32.9	4.8	25.2	12.7	121.5	274.6	77.7	1.8	27.0	2.9	11.5	0.9	6.1	2.4	4.1
2M1/11	0.03	0.23	23.2	38.0	15.5	52.1	159.0	41.2	60.3	1.6	39.9	8.9	4.9	5.3	7.6	3.8	2.1
2M2/11	0.29	0.42	52.7	48.9	18.6	36.8	405.8	26.0	58.2	4.4	14.2	8.9	8.9	1.6	1.2	1.2	0.6
6MO/12	0.04	0.14	28.8	21.5	2.2	52.6	285.4	11.6	51.0	1.8	29.3	13.1	9.7	3.6	6.6	3.6	0.2
5O/12	0.01	0.03	10.0	4.9	0.7	16.2	162.4	11.5	26.7	2.0	31.8	3.0	5.3	2.1	2.9	4.3	2.3
4MO/12	0.22	0.22	25.2	28.7	3.7	96.9	242.9	34.1	65.4	0.6	22.7	8.5	10.2	2.0	3.5	2.9	2.0
7O/13	0.03	0.27	8.7	182.3	23.0	512.8	118.8	24.1	43.8	2.3	24.4	8.4	12.7	1.9	2.3	2.5	2.4
6MO/13	0.12	0.12	7.2	40.6	4.6	76.7	152.5	19.2	48.9	0.9	23.9	7.0	4.4	2.0	6.0	4.8	2.1
5O/13	0.11	0.10	24.9	31.7	6.3	152.3	198.2	74.6	68.1	2.8	36.1	5.6	4.1	3.3	7.0	4.9	1.4
4MO/13	0.03	0.06	4.0	8.2	0.5	22.9	147.8	11.5	44.4	0.5	35.8	4.0	8.0	1.7	3.0	6.0	2.2
PD mean	<i>0.16</i>	<i>0.20</i>	<i>23.6</i>	<i>67.9</i>	<i>8.5</i>	<i>164.6</i>	<i>189.8</i>	<i>80.1</i>	<i>67.6</i>	<i>2.1</i>	<i>25.5</i>	<i>10.4</i>	<i>10.3</i>	<i>2.3</i>	<i>4.0</i>	<i>2.9</i>	<i>1.8</i>
4M/14	0.19	0.22	28.0	36.0	0.7	118.0	196.0	44.2	26.4	2.3	14.1	6.2	6.9	3.7	1.2	0.6	0.6
2I/15	0.29	0.11	26.7	69.2	21.0	192.1	148.3	197.0	220.2	0.4	34.2	31.3	29.7	7.5	10.8	9.0	2.0
3K/15	0.04	0.18	3.6	55.5	1.3	218.0	108.9	31.0	30.9	1.6	37.1	16.4	19.4	1.6	4.0	2.2	0.2
2K/16	0.42	0.15	36.4	98.1	16.5	170.3	186.0	40.6	34.2	0.3	29.6	39.5	37.0	6.1	7.4	6.9	3.6
3I/16	0.43	0.14	34.0	79.3	9.9	150.2	99.6	251.0	124.8	1.4	25.1	19.0	20.8	9.6	13.6	3.0	2.5
MN mean	<i>0.27</i>	<i>0.16</i>	<i>25.7</i>	<i>67.2</i>	<i>9.8</i>	<i>169.7</i>	<i>147.8</i>	<i>112.7</i>	<i>87.3</i>	<i>1.2</i>	<i>28.0</i>	<i>24.0</i>	<i>22.7</i>	<i>5.7</i>	<i>7.4</i>	<i>4.3</i>	<i>1.8</i>
Total mean	<i>0.18</i>	<i>0.19</i>	<i>23.9</i>	<i>67.8</i>	<i>8.7</i>	<i>165.1</i>	<i>185.3</i>	<i>83.6</i>	<i>69.7</i>	<i>2.0</i>	<i>25.8</i>	<i>11.9</i>	<i>11.6</i>	<i>2.7</i>	<i>4.4</i>	<i>3.1</i>	<i>1.8</i>
CC	--	--	0.09	--	0.12	--	--	--	0.08	0.07	0.55	0.12	0.08	0.16	0.15	0.18	0.19
World range	--	--	1-3000	--	5-300	--	--	--	--	5-300	5-400	10-500	20-1000	0.5-60	2-100	0.5-50	2-80
Hard coal avg.	--	--	250	--	71	--	--	--	890	28	47	100	150	17	28	17	9.0
LODs	0.7	0.5	0.9	0.1	0.1	0.2	1.2	0.6	0.1	0.1	0.6	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.1

Notes: Values in boldface are below Swaine's world ranges in coal; mean values in cursive; LODs = detection limits ($\mu\text{g/g}$)

Table 4: Concentrations ($\mu\text{g/g}$), average values and concentration coefficients (CC) of trace elements in Marcelina coal samples determined by ICP-MS.

Sample	Li	Be	U	Co	Cu	Ga	Ge	As	Rb	Zr	Nb	Mo	Sb	Cs	W	Th	Se
5O/1	4.71	0.453	0.430	2.39	4.21	2.95	1.32	0.696	2.39	11.50	1.66	1.58	0.342	0.106	0.263	0.726	0.542
3K/2	0.980	0.251	0.082	0.374	2.11	0.661	1.58	0.298	0.160	3.078	0.232	0.110	0.093	0.006	0.106	0.243	1.18
2M/2	0.541	0.301	0.095	0.638	3.03	0.752	1.55	0.089	0.339	3.596	0.354	0.289	0.901	0.013	0.089	0.167	0.604
4MO/3	5.04	0.100	0.148	0.560	3.24	0.841	0.235	0.114	0.257	4.303	0.334	0.202	0.872	0.016	0.053	0.284	0.796
2O/3	3.05	0.109	0.199	0.507	0.722	0.710	0.086	0.198	0.095	2.780	0.262	0.498	0.049	0.007	0.055	0.436	0.671
7O/4	0.929	0.130	0.083	0.257	0.872	0.429	0.349	0.095	0.215	2.652	0.248	0.037	0.061	0.019	0.082	0.173	2.00
6M/4	4.55	0.214	0.124	0.501	2.57	0.885	0.264	0.223	0.268	3.863	0.468	0.434	0.083	0.020	0.069	0.217	0.851
6O/4	5.99	0.529	0.219	0.785	4.90	2.91	2.01	0.555	0.799	5.414	0.748	1.353	0.530	0.069	0.083	0.389	0.981
6Q/4	8.61	0.593	0.101	1.30	0.293	2.50	1.78	0.165	2.01	7.581	3.18	0.863	1.14	0.091	0.503	0.245	0.830
5O/4	3.70	0.160	0.159	0.633	3.22	0.983	0.588	0.117	0.213	4.775	0.404	0.443	0.229	0.010	0.075	0.268	0.771
4MO/4	2.20	0.157	0.081	0.296	1.02	0.346	0.744	0.032	0.085	1.858	0.181	0.106	0.069	0.004	0.206	0.195	0.728
7O/5	2.36	0.379	0.113	0.449	2.36	0.684	1.41	0.274	0.675	8.098	0.416	0.304	0.113	0.058	0.086	0.201	0.904
6MO/5	6.20	0.102	0.167	0.684	2.86	0.709	0.555	0.518	0.998	3.368	0.316	0.645	0.091	0.078	0.046	0.326	1.04
6Q/5	1.82	0.027	0.049	0.252	1.89	2.08	0.451	0.063	0.158	2.016	0.162	0.262	0.061	0.006	0.086	0.137	0.786
5O/5	0.972	0.780	0.118	1.70	2.24	2.16	2.90	0.665	0.991	12.00	0.228	1.49	0.520	0.069	0.084	0.351	0.923
4MO/5	2.77	0.089	0.067	0.322	2.01	0.382	0.193	0.078	0.187	1.834	0.156	0.295	0.047	0.008	0.029	0.126	0.660
5M/6	1.90	0.247	0.069	0.425	0.605	0.537	1.64	0.159	0.170	5.494	0.441	0.521	0.267	0.023	0.122	0.124	1.03
4M/6	2.59	0.083	0.088	0.372	0.740	0.585	0.843	0.138	0.092	2.677	0.240	0.352	0.254	0.008	0.063	0.199	0.763
4O/6	6.92	0.352	0.176	1.06	2.28	0.293	2.25	0.957	0.258	9.326	0.583	2.13	0.582	0.022	0.151	0.314	1.452
7O/7	2.01	0.248	0.168	0.511	3.60	0.710	2.60	0.137	0.954	3.293	0.348	0.449	0.114	0.066	0.096	0.287	0.793
6MO/7	12.1	0.470	0.134	1.58	3.07	1.62	1.70	0.277	0.281	8.858	0.701	0.817	0.784	0.021	0.120	0.228	0.959
4M/7	1.77	0.334	0.078	0.509	4.73	0.497	0.494	0.289	0.219	1.563	0.686	0.372	0.115	0.017	0.078	0.134	1.83
3K/8	1.42	0.629	0.192	1.30	3.78	1.14	0.604	0.373	1.32	6.656	0.150	0.896	0.455	0.081	0.196	0.325	0.666
7O/9	3.56	0.158	0.073	0.320	1.16	0.331	0.825	0.171	0.154	2.424	0.184	0.425	0.053	0.012	0.051	0.182	0.840
6MO/9	3.20	0.070	0.148	0.686	1.09	0.693	0.210	0.334	0.647	3.129	0.442	0.938	0.122	0.053	0.087	0.271	0.981
5O/9	1.72	0.418	0.079	0.719	0.484	1.01	0.894	0.423	0.191	6.892	0.327	0.184	0.447	0.017	0.108	0.137	0.782
4M/9	2.44	0.027	0.065	0.257	0.824	0.434	0.126	0.060	0.054	1.933	0.152	0.081	0.079	0.006	0.039	0.123	1.00
4O/9	1.29	0.047	0.054	0.526	2.90	0.388	0.741	0.179	0.260	1.718	0.188	0.097	0.154	0.012	0.064	0.127	0.849
6MO/10	3.02	0.053	0.102	0.365	3.08	0.385	0.068	0.206	0.468	2.182	0.219	0.697	1.036	0.034	0.032	0.172	1.01
5O/10	1.62	0.324	0.115	0.656	0.742	0.684	2.10	0.076	0.192	5.254	0.440	0.142	0.884	0.017	0.090	0.194	0.949
4MO/10	3.23	0.146	0.234	0.805	3.29	2.21	0.629	0.360	2.65	5.585	0.722	0.496	0.168	0.103	0.153	0.401	1.10

Sample	Li	Be	U	Co	Cu	Ga	Ge	As	Rb	Zr	Nb	Mo	Sb	Cs	W	Th	Se
3K/11	15.5	0.316	0.144	0.915	0.709	1.00	2.01	0.084	1.16	6.760	3.48	0.261	0.834	0.085	0.333	0.246	0.913
2M1/11	1.99	0.653	0.203	1.80	0.661	1.69	1.43	0.356	0.952	7.590	0.689	0.085	0.569	0.062	0.095	0.371	0.735
2M2/11	2.06	0.028	0.076	0.385	0.752	0.429	0.078	0.178	0.041	2.005	0.162	0.086	0.069	0.004	0.018	0.185	0.696
6MO/12	4.27	0.335	0.173	0.997	0.841	1.52	0.705	0.261	0.296	5.270	0.333	0.656	0.244	0.025	0.066	0.292	0.938
5O/12	1.95	0.414	0.098	0.803	0.710	1.04	2.95	0.068	0.405	6.422	1.89	0.441	0.178	0.017	0.122	0.292	1.44
4MO/12	4.78	0.238	0.108	0.679	0.429	0.958	0.876	0.753	0.289	4.476	0.374	0.300	0.320	0.013	0.051	0.282	1.06
7O/13	5.01	0.234	0.132	0.667	0.885	0.524	1.14	0.167	0.443	2.971	0.233	0.154	1.09	0.029	0.078	0.292	0.693
6MO/13	4.57	0.192	0.186	0.736	2.91	0.554	0.576	0.267	0.213	2.574	0.266	0.628	0.253	0.012	0.054	0.484	1.03
5O/13	2.51	0.665	0.160	1.18	0.831	1.40	1.00	0.210	1.52	11.01	0.272	0.285	0.409	0.013	0.123	0.281	0.700
4MO/13	7.57	0.458	0.151	1.69	0.983	1.43	1.85	0.108	0.108	5.266	0.641	0.363	0.802	0.007	0.134	0.289	1.00
PD mean	<i>3.74</i>	<i>0.281</i>	<i>0.144</i>	<i>0.783</i>	<i>1.94</i>	<i>1.03</i>	<i>1.08</i>	<i>0.262</i>	<i>0.564</i>	<i>4.879</i>	<i>0.572</i>	<i>0.51</i>	<i>0.38</i>	<i>0.033</i>	<i>0.109</i>	<i>0.264</i>	<i>0.94</i>
4M/14	1.49	0.042	0.121	0.401	0.346	0.494	0.371	0.309	0.504	2.161	0.313	0.075	0.093	0.052	0.039	0.311	1.10
2I/15	5.23	0.692	0.356	3.02	0.684	1.97	3.53	0.248	1.06	13.64	1.68	0.158	0.510	0.101	0.192	0.604	0.694
3K/15	1.97	0.475	0.284	0.574	2.95	1.30	2.92	0.562	0.528	7.828	0.381	0.303	0.815	0.033	0.121	0.479	0.834
2K/16	1.56	0.237	0.406	0.765	1.81	0.831	1.52	0.255	0.243	11.35	4.18	0.279	0.413	0.115	0.190	0.725	0.774
3I/16	19.7	0.194	0.381	2.52	2.16	3.32	3.82	0.432	1.84	15.77	0.620	1.06	0.353	0.109	0.155	0.647	0.801
MN mean	<i>5.99</i>	<i>0.328</i>	<i>0.216</i>	<i>0.889</i>	<i>1.59</i>	<i>1.58</i>	<i>2.43</i>	<i>0.361</i>	<i>0.84</i>	<i>10.15</i>	<i>1.43</i>	<i>0.37</i>	<i>0.436</i>	<i>0.082</i>	<i>0.139</i>	<i>0.553</i>	<i>0.84</i>
Total mean	<i>3.98</i>	<i>0.286</i>	<i>0.152</i>	<i>0.866</i>	<i>1.91</i>	<i>1.08</i>	<i>1.23</i>	<i>0.273</i>	<i>0.59</i>	<i>5.45</i>	<i>0.67</i>	<i>0.49</i>	<i>0.39</i>	<i>0.038</i>	<i>0.112</i>	<i>0.292</i>	<i>0.93</i>
CC	0.28	0.14	0.08	0.14	0.12	0.18	0.51	0.03	0.03	0.15	0.16	0.23	0.39	0.03	0.11	0.07	0.58
World range	1-80	0.1-15	0.5-10	0.5-30	0.5-50	1-20	0.5-50	0.5-80	2-50	5-200	1-20	0.1-10	0.1-10	0.3-5	0.5-5	0.5-10	0.2-10
Hard coal av.	14	2.0	1.9	6.0	16	6.0	2.4	9.0	18	36	4.0	2.1	1.00	1.1	0.99	3.2	1.6
LODs	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.3

Note: As and Se were determined by using collision/reaction cell technology (CCT) of ICP-MS according to Li et al. (2014). Detection limits (LODs) expressed in ng/g.

Table 5: Contents in µg/g, means and concentration coefficients (CC) for rare-earth elements (REEs) analyzed in Marcelina coal samples by ICP-MS.

Sample	La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Sm	Eu	Gd	Tb	Dy	Ho	Er	Tm	Yb	Lu	Y	Sc
5O/1	2.15	5.92	0.979	2.04	0.567	0.116	0.428	0.099	0.549	0.108	0.294	0.043	0.474	0.041	2.56	0.679
3K/2	0.367	0.677	0.081	0.321	0.077	0.038	0.302	0.050	0.227	0.133	0.133	0.020	0.126	0.018	0.209	0.405
2M/2	0.323	0.638	0.074	0.307	0.073	0.021	0.103	0.018	0.122	0.028	0.084	0.012	0.085	0.012	0.744	0.356
4MO/3	0.752	1.35	0.148	0.547	0.098	0.022	0.099	0.013	0.079	0.015	0.043	0.006	0.041	0.005	0.384	0.135
2O/3	0.569	1.03	0.111	0.425	0.083	0.019	0.087	0.012	0.070	0.039	0.039	0.005	0.036	0.005	0.368	0.120
6M/4	0.415	0.779	0.086	0.337	0.069	0.017	0.091	0.015	0.102	0.023	0.070	0.010	0.068	0.010	0.583	0.243
6O/4	0.616	1.06	0.118	0.440	0.092	0.027	0.118	0.023	0.139	0.034	0.096	0.017	0.098	0.016	0.718	0.346
6Q/4	0.875	1.86	0.248	1.04	0.242	0.069	0.263	0.041	0.226	0.050	0.135	0.022	0.128	0.021	1.14	0.631
5O/4	1.38	2.01	0.317	0.723	0.328	0.055	0.204	0.045	0.366	0.181	0.514	0.063	0.419	0.084	2.34	0.964
4MO/4	0.838	1.51	0.171	0.651	0.128	0.031	0.131	0.019	0.105	0.021	0.056	0.008	0.054	0.007	0.482	0.212
7O/4	0.305	0.562	0.062	0.239	0.047	0.012	0.058	0.009	0.057	0.012	0.037	0.005	0.036	0.005	0.355	0.130
7O/5	0.667	1.21	0.138	0.530	0.106	0.026	0.130	0.022	0.152	0.036	0.108	0.016	0.113	0.016	0.895	0.355
6MO/5	1.03	2.02	0.227	0.877	0.168	0.038	0.159	0.023	0.128	0.025	0.070	0.010	0.065	0.009	0.556	0.182
6Q/5	0.290	0.537	0.058	0.219	0.051	0.020	0.105	0.021	0.080	0.023	0.054	0.014	0.056	0.014	0.417	0.254
5O/5	0.668	1.24	0.160	0.717	0.207	0.069	0.357	0.070	0.517	0.127	0.406	0.066	0.284	0.072	2.17	0.712
4MO/5	0.435	0.772	0.085	0.318	0.057	0.014	0.056	0.008	0.042	0.008	0.024	0.003	0.023	0.003	0.204	0.078
5M/6	0.520	0.956	0.111	0.408	0.084	0.011	0.035	0.005	0.028	0.006	0.015	0.002	0.015	0.002	0.147	0.046
4M/6	0.396	0.713	0.078	0.295	0.056	0.014	0.058	0.008	0.048	0.029	0.029	0.004	0.029	0.004	0.269	0.155
4O/6	2.66	4.21	0.472	1.78	0.310	0.026	0.080	0.012	0.085	0.019	0.058	0.009	0.061	0.009	0.530	0.235
7O/7	0.660	1.21	0.138	0.532	0.109	0.032	0.125	0.021	0.121	0.026	0.077	0.011	0.075	0.011	0.687	0.284
6MO/7	0.620	0.993	0.124	0.505	0.131	0.042	0.158	0.032	0.167	0.041	0.107	0.021	0.105	0.020	0.832	0.546
4M/7	0.439	0.796	0.092	0.361	0.073	0.018	0.089	0.013	0.082	0.018	0.053	0.007	0.048	0.007	0.560	0.138
3K/8	1.143	2.17	0.261	1.05	0.225	0.061	0.289	0.047	0.319	0.073	0.219	0.033	0.212	0.032	1.92	0.778
7O/9	0.449	0.854	0.096	0.369	0.068	0.017	0.079	0.011	0.074	0.017	0.051	0.007	0.053	0.007	0.491	0.174
6MO/9	1.13	2.05	0.228	0.824	0.146	0.035	0.141	0.022	0.106	0.025	0.063	0.012	0.061	0.012	0.477	0.178
5O/9	0.753	1.28	0.134	0.482	0.093	0.024	0.112	0.019	0.121	0.029	0.087	0.015	0.096	0.015	0.712	0.464
4M/9	0.211	0.392	0.046	0.174	0.037	0.010	0.037	0.006	0.029	0.007	0.016	0.004	0.016	0.003	0.125	0.056
4O/9	0.244	0.472	0.055	0.220	0.046	0.012	0.044	0.007	0.032	0.008	0.020	0.004	0.020	0.004	0.164	0.079
6MO/10	0.454	0.859	0.097	0.365	0.069	0.015	0.069	0.009	0.053	0.010	0.029	0.004	0.029	0.004	0.239	0.072
5O/10	0.339	0.647	0.075	0.299	0.067	0.018	0.084	0.015	0.097	0.023	0.071	0.011	0.078	0.011	0.594	0.345
4MO/10	1.62	2.89	0.336	1.28	0.237	0.053	0.226	0.031	0.181	0.037	0.107	0.016	0.106	0.015	1.17	0.251

Sample	La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Sm	Eu	Gd	Tb	Dy	Ho	Er	Tm	Yb	Lu	Y	Sc
3K/11	1.00	3.56	1.02	1.50	0.539	0.103	0.464	0.084	0.596	0.147	0.216	0.081	0.251	0.033	0.871	0.297
2M1/11	1.42	2.83	0.323	1.30	0.303	0.048	0.132	0.022	0.149	0.035	0.107	0.017	0.115	0.017	0.877	0.477
2M2/11	0.535	0.966	0.108	0.405	0.075	0.018	0.054	0.009	0.048	0.009	0.024	0.003	0.022	0.003	0.887	0.069
6MO/12	0.622	1.17	0.141	0.570	0.129	0.040	0.161	0.029	0.157	0.036	0.097	0.016	0.090	0.015	0.857	0.376
5O/12	0.363	0.647	0.075	0.307	0.065	0.017	0.083	0.014	0.101	0.024	0.074	0.011	0.080	0.012	0.622	0.395
4MO/12	0.612	1.13	0.127	0.489	0.098	0.024	0.111	0.017	0.104	0.022	0.064	0.009	0.062	0.009	0.553	0.258
7O/13	0.512	0.972	0.109	0.430	0.087	0.023	0.114	0.019	0.130	0.032	0.099	0.015	0.102	0.015	0.842	0.280
6MO/13	0.541	1.01	0.116	0.463	0.099	0.025	0.120	0.018	0.110	0.025	0.071	0.010	0.066	0.010	0.649	0.249
5O/13	0.816	1.54	0.182	0.072	0.152	0.039	0.180	0.029	0.195	0.144	0.144	0.023	0.158	0.024	1.18	0.716
4MO/13	1.13	2.03	0.227	0.852	0.150	0.029	0.164	0.024	0.153	0.034	0.101	0.015	0.101	0.014	0.854	0.487
PD mean	<i>0.75</i>	<i>1.45</i>	<i>0.19</i>	<i>0.61</i>	<i>0.141</i>	<i>0.032</i>	<i>0.144</i>	<i>0.023</i>	<i>0.152</i>	<i>0.042</i>	<i>0.101</i>	<i>0.016</i>	<i>0.102</i>	<i>0.016</i>	<i>0.76</i>	<i>0.326</i>
4M/14	0.473	0.953	0.208	0.169	0.101	0.014	0.114	0.019	0.107	0.027	0.031	0.010	0.075	0.018	0.299	0.080
2I/15	1.24	1.82	0.501	1.18	0.506	0.112	0.539	0.108	0.580	0.095	0.507	0.038	0.372	0.052	1.87	0.237
3K/15	0.602	0.990	0.117	0.483	0.118	0.052	0.399	0.062	0.332	0.074	0.213	0.031	0.206	0.030	0.818	0.499
2K/16	0.344	0.556	0.064	0.249	0.053	0.014	0.065	0.011	0.075	0.018	0.037	0.029	0.063	0.009	0.431	0.206
3I/16	1.40	2.00	0.042	1.35	0.292	0.068	0.222	0.041	0.324	0.107	0.176	0.039	0.308	0.068	1.90	0.408
MN mean	<i>0.81</i>	<i>1.26</i>	<i>0.187</i>	<i>0.686</i>	<i>0.211</i>	<i>0.052</i>	<i>0.263</i>	<i>0.047</i>	<i>0.283</i>	<i>0.064</i>	<i>0.192</i>	<i>0.029</i>	<i>0.204</i>	<i>0.035</i>	<i>1.06</i>	<i>0.286</i>
Total mean	<i>0.76</i>	<i>1.43</i>	<i>0.19</i>	<i>0.61</i>	<i>0.149</i>	<i>0.035</i>	<i>0.157</i>	<i>0.026</i>	<i>0.167</i>	<i>0.045</i>	<i>0.111</i>	<i>0.017</i>	<i>0.113</i>	<i>0.018</i>	<i>0.79</i>	<i>0.322</i>
CC	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.07	0.08	0.06	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.11	0.06	0.11	0.09	0.10	0.09
World range	1-40	2-70	1-10	3-30	0.5-6	0.1-2	0-4	0.1-1	0.5-4	0.1-2	0.5-3	0.1-1	0.3-3	0.05-1	2-50	1-10
Hard coal av.	11	23	3.4	12	2.2	0.43	2.7	0.31	2.1	0.57	1.00	0.30	1.0	0.20	8.2	3.7
Chondrite	310	808	122	600	195	73.5	259	47.4	322	71.8	210	32.4	209	32	--	--
LODs	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2

Notes: Chondrite values used to normalize concentrations of REE; LODs expressed in ng/g.

Table 6: Elemental affinities deduced from the Pearson correlations.

Significant correlation with ash yield ($r > + 0.50$) Al, P, K, Ti, Sr, Ba, Cr, V, U, Co, Ga, Rb, Zr, Nb, Cs, W, Th, Pr, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er, Yb, and Lu
Weak or no correlation with ash yield ($0 < r < + 0.50$) Fe, Ca, Mg, Na, Mn, B, Zn, Ni, Pb, Li, Be, Cu, Ge, As, Mo, Sb, La, Ce, Nd, Tm, Y, and Sc
Inverse correlation with ash yield ($r = - 0.35$) Se

Table 7: Ranges of metal ratios of Marcelina coals compared to the ratios in sediments sourced from mafic rocks and felsic rocks, as well as values for El Carmen and El Palmar granitoids.

Ratio	Coal samples	Mafic sources	Felsic sources	El Carmen	El Palmar
La/Sc	0.91 – 11.31	0.43 – 0.86	2.50 – 16.3	5.51	4.55
Th/Sc	0.25 – 3.89	0.05 – 0.22	0.84 – 20.5	1.48	0.40
La/Co	0.41 – 2.51	0.14 – 0.38	1.8 – 13.8	8.72	7.81
Th/Cr	0.049 – 0.312	0.018 – 0.046	0.13 – 2.70	2.56	0.60

Note: Data from granitoids after Van Der Lelij (2013).

Table 8: Mineral content in some coals from sampled seams as deduced from semiquantitative X-ray analysis plus total clay and illite contents. Data in wt.% of LTA residue (+++ = dominant phase > 20 wt.%; ++ = abundant phase 3-20 wt.%; + = minor phase 1-3 wt.%; O = accessory phase < 1 wt.%).

Sample	Kln	Ill	Rct	Py	Sp	Qtz	Ap	Kfs	Pl	Ank	Sd	Dsp	Bas	Hem	Whe	But	Clay	Illite
5O/1	+++	O	O	O	O	+++	+	O	+	O	O	O	O	O	O	O	46.0	0.5
2M/2	+++	+	--	O	O	+++	--	--	O	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	43.0	2.8
2O/3	+++	++	O	O	--	+++	--	--	O	O	--	--	O	--	O	--	40.0	4.6
6M/4	+++	O	--	O	--	+++	O	--	O	O	O	--	--	O	--	--	43.0	0.7
6O/4	+++	O	O	O	--	+++	O	O	O	O	O	--	--	O	--	--	50.0	0.6
6Q/5	+++	O	O	O	--	+++	+	--	O	--	--	O	--	--	--	--	40.0	0.8
5M/6	+++	O	O	O	O	+++	--	O	O	O	O	--	O	--	O	--	52.0	0.6
7O/7	+++	O	O	O	--	+++	O	O	O	+	O	--	O	O	O	O	53.0	0.7
3K/8	+++	+	O	O	O	+++	O	O	O	+	O	--	O	O	O	O	43.0	1.1
4O/9	+++	O	O	O	--	+++	O	O	O	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	55.0	0.9
4MO/10	+++	O	O	O	O	+++	O	+	O	O	O	--	--	O	--	O	40.0	0.7
6MO/12	+++	O	--	O	--	+++	O	--	O	--	O	--	--	--	--	--	53.0	0.8
4M/14	+++	O	O	O	O	+++	O	O	O	--	O	--	--	--	--	O	76.0	0.7
2I/15	+++	+	O	O	--	+++	O	+	+	O	--	--	--	--	--	--	70.0	1.3
2K/16	+++	+	O	O	--	+++	O	O	--	O	O	O	--	--	--	--	68.0	1.2
3I/16	+++	++	O	O	--	+++	O	+	--	O	--	O	--	--	--	--	62.0	4.9

Notes: Mineral abbreviations after Kretz (1983): Kln = kaolinite; Ill = illite; Rct = smectite; Ap = apatite; Sd = siderite; Kfs = k-feldspar; Py = pyrite; Pl = plagioclase; Sp = spharelite; Qtz = quartz; Bas = bassanite; Dsp = diaspore; Whe = whewellite; Hem = hematite; Ank = ankerite; But = butlerite.

Appendix A. Total, light REE and heavy REE contents ($\mu\text{g/g}$), Ce and Eu anomalies as well as element ratios in Guasare coals.

Sample	Ca/Sr	Ni/Co	Th/Sc	Th/Cr	La/Co	La/Sc	REY	LREE	HREE	Ce _n /Ce*	Eu _n /Eu*	(Gd/Yb) _n
5O/1	24.55	3.47	1.07	0.121	0.90	3.16	16.36	11.77	4.592	0.99	0.62	0.72
3K/2	6.54	2.93	0.57	0.221	0.92	0.91	2.779	1.561	1.218	0.93	0.84	1.93
2M/2	4.22	3.28	0.47	0.119	0.50	0.91	2.644	1.436	1.208	0.98	0.76	0.98
4MO/3	7.31	3.92	2.10	0.158	1.34	5.56	3.599	2.915	0.685	0.94	0.70	1.94
2O/3	41.53	1.97	3.63	0.311	1.12	4.75	2.893	2.232	0.661	0.95	0.70	1.95
7O/4	15.61	3.88	0.71	0.157	1.62	1.71	2.675	1.703	0.972	0.97	0.68	1.08
6M/4	10.88	1.19	0.63	0.108	1.23	1.78	3.608	2.349	1.259	0.92	0.77	0.97
6O/4	17.16	1.78	0.62	0.177	1.11	1.39	6.359	4.334	2.024	0.97	0.84	1.66
6Q/4	3.99	4.67	0.25	0.049	1.06	1.44	9.030	4.817	4.213	0.73	0.52	0.39
5O/4	6.52	6.94	1.26	0.167	1.32	3.95	4.215	3.332	0.883	0.94	0.74	1.96
4MO/4	6.02	6.42	1.50	0.093	1.03	2.35	1.801	1.227	0.574	0.96	0.73	1.30
7O/5	34.75	5.11	0.57	0.087	1.48	1.88	4.160	2.672	1.488	0.93	0.68	0.93
6MO/5	21.00	2.92	1.79	0.136	1.50	5.66	5.396	4.351	1.045	0.99	0.70	1.97
6Q/5	14.51	7.53	0.54	0.098	1.14	1.13	1.959	1.175	0.784	0.97	0.85	1.49
5O/5	4.18	2.94	0.49	0.066	0.41	0.94	7.135	4.072	3.063	0.91	0.78	1.02
4MO/5	7.35	4.65	1.62	0.084	1.35	5.58	2.052	1.681	0.371	0.94	0.76	1.96
5M/6	4.70	8.46	2.69	0.073	1.22	11.30	2.344	2.089	0.255	0.94	0.46	1.89
4M/6	26.85	2.95	1.28	0.132	1.06	2.55	2.030	1.552	0.478	0.95	0.77	1.61
4O/6	20.32	3.59	1.34	0.131	2.51	11.31	10.32	9.454	0.863	0.87	0.31	1.06
7O/7	25.95	4.89	1.01	0.151	1.29	2.32	3.836	2.682	1.154	0.94	0.84	1.34
6MO/7	16.35	3.79	0.42	0.074	0.41	1.13	3.898	2.415	1.483	0.84	0.85	1.21
4M/7	4.52	2.94	0.97	0.071	0.86	3.18	2.656	1.779	0.877	0.93	0.72	1.49
3K/8	25.56	2.76	0.41	0.105	0.88	1.47	8.052	4.911	3.141	0.95	0.75	1.10
7O/9	8.42	2.18	1.05	0.152	1.41	2.58	2.643	1.853	0.790	0.98	0.74	1.20
6MO/9	10.82	1.74	1.52	0.118	1.65	6.34	5.336	4.416	0.919	0.95	0.73	1.86
5O/9	4.60	7.64	0.30	0.072	1.04	1.63	3.976	2.769	1.206	0.93	0.73	0.94
4M/9	15.62	3.49	2.19	0.068	0.82	3.77	1.113	0.870	0.243	0.95	0.81	1.87
4O/9	3.68	4.93	1.61	0.091	0.46	3.09	1.351	1.049	0.303	0.97	0.79	1.77
6MO/10	7.65	4.37	2.39	0.107	1.25	6.31	2.305	1.859	0.446	0.97	0.68	1.91
5O/10	16.30	8.38	0.56	0.121	0.51	0.99	2.429	1.445	0.984	0.96	0.73	0.87
4MO/10	10.06	3.22	1.59	0.098	2.02	6.47	8.306	6.415	1.891	0.92	0.70	1.72
3K/11	4.37	2.62	0.83	0.273	1.09	3.37	10.47	7.728	2.743	0.76	0.55	1.49

Sample	Ca/Sr	Ni/Co	Th/Sc	Th/Cr	La/Co	La/Sc	REY	LREE	HREE	Ce _n /Ce*	Eu _n /Eu*	(Gd/Yb) _n
2M1/11	5.85	2.11	0.78	0.070	0.79	2.97	7.690	6.219	1.471	0.99	0.55	0.93
2M2/11	4.13	3.11	2.68	0.116	1.39	7.76	3.166	2.107	1.059	0.94	0.76	1.98
6MO/12	4.01	3.61	0.77	0.081	0.62	1.65	4.133	2.674	1.458	0.95	0.84	1.44
5O/12	5.40	5.35	0.70	0.139	0.43	0.91	2.495	1.474	1.021	0.92	0.72	0.84
4MO/12	11.40	4.27	1.09	0.141	0.90	2.37	3.430	2.479	0.951	0.96	0.72	1.44
7O/13	61.04	3.75	1.04	0.154	0.77	1.83	3.501	2.133	1.368	0.97	0.73	0.90
6MO/13	10.95	6.51	1.94	0.242	0.73	2.17	3.328	2.249	1.079	0.95	0.73	1.47
5O/13	27.19	4.16	0.39	0.085	0.69	1.14	4.874	2.799	2.075	0.95	0.73	0.92
4MO/13	5.72	3.55	0.59	0.170	0.67	2.31	5.873	4.412	1.460	0.94	0.58	1.31
4M/14	19.03	1.49	3.89	0.084	1.18	5.90	2.618	1.918	0.700	0.79	0.40	1.22
2I/15	6.13	2.97	2.55	0.081	0.51	5.20	9.509	5.350	4.159	0.63	0.61	1.17
3K/15	13.29	3.83	0.96	0.299	1.05	1.21	4.527	2.362	2.165	0.97	0.84	1.56
2K/16	4.31	9.02	3.52	0.119	0.47	1.67	2.018	1.280	0.738	0.95	0.74	0.83
3I/16	7.90	1.19	1.59	0.067	0.56	3.42	9.025	4.921	3.184	0.72	0.72	0.58

Notes: REY defined as sum of REE and Y; LREE defined as sum of La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, and Eu; HREE defined as sum of Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er, Tm, Yb, Lu, and Y; Ce_n/Ce* and Eu_n/Eu*, with Ce* and Eu* equal to $0.5 \cdot La_n + 0.5 \cdot Pr_n$ and $0.67 \cdot Sm_n + 0.33 \cdot Tb_n$ (Mishra et al., 2019).

Appendix B. Detailed calculations used to determine mean gas content for Guasare coals

(1) A hypothetical coal “molecule” was assumed to contain 10000 atoms of carbon in the initial state of high-volatile bituminous rank (for which the starting H/C and O/C atomic ratios appear to be 0.85 and 0.13). Thus, the number of hydrogen and oxygen atoms present in the initial high-volatile bituminous coal “molecule” would be 8500 and 1300. The aim is to calculate how many molecules of methane would be released during the transition from the beginning of high-volatile bituminous rank to the average maturity level for Guasare coals.

(2) Let: X = the number of molecules of CH_4 generated; Y = the number of molecules of CO_2 generated, and Z = the number of molecules of H_2O generated. For example, each molecule of CO_2 evolved removes 2 oxygen atoms for every carbon atom removed from the coal “molecule”. At the average maturity level for Guasare coals: the number of carbon atoms that remain equals to $10000 - X - Y$; the number of H atoms that remain equals to $8500 - 4X - 2Z$; and the number of O atoms that remain equals to $1300 - 2Y - Z$.

(3) The next step is to calculate how many molecules of CH_4 , CO_2 and H_2O must be generated to reach the H/C and O/C atomic ratios (0.782 and 0.066) at the average maturity level for Guasare coals. The following equations can be used:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{H/C} = 0.782 &= (8500 - 4X - 2Z)/(10000 - X - Y) \\ \text{O/C} = 0.066 &= (1300 - 2Y - Z)/(10000 - X - Y). \end{aligned}$$

(4) The above equations are solved in terms of Y and Z by fixing X at a constant number of molecules of CH_4 generated:

$$\begin{aligned} 3.218X - 680 &= 0.782Y - 2Z \\ 0.066X + 640 &= 1.934Y + Z. \end{aligned}$$

(5) Both equations are solved for Y by standard methods:

$$Y = (3.35X + 600)/4.65$$

(6) A latter equation can be applied when considering the high-volatile bituminous A rank of Guasare coals:

$$Y = 2X$$

(7) The solution to the latter two equations is accomplished and the result is approximately 100 molecules of CH_4 generated per coal “molecule” containing 10000, 8500 and 1300, respectively, carbon, hydrogen and oxygen atoms.

(8) Assuming the International Standard Metric Conditions for natural gas (288.15 K and 1 atm) and applying the ideal gas law, a quantity of $\sim 16 \text{ cm}^3$ per gram of raw coal is obtained. Then, if we also assumed a mass loss of around one third during the transition from lignite to high-volatile bituminous A coal, the amount of methane generated would be about $11 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$.

(9) Finally, considering the estimation of coal reserves for the study area (~ 1600 million tons), it can be preliminarily concluded that coalbed methane reserves in the Guasare Coalfield would be close to 17.6 billion cubic meters.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

CRedit author statement

Gonzalo Márquez: Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft, Investigation, Supervision; **Manuel Martínez:** Writing - Review & Editing, Formal analysis, Validation; **Gabriela Carruyo:** Visualization, Investigation; **Carlos Boente:** Writing - Review & Editing, Formal analysis; **Erika Lorenzo:** Investigation, Data curation; **Rafael Tocco:** Writing - Review & Editing, Resources.